

HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-01-14– GA 101136095

Demonstrating large pit thermal energy storages and improving their components, processes, and procedures for an accelerated realization of 100 % sustainable district heating networks in Europe.

D6.1: Ecological Implications of PTES

Document Information	
Due Date:	2026-03-31
Actual Submission Date:	2026-03-24
Type of Deliverable (Report/Data/DEC/Ethics):	Report
Dissemination Level (Public/Sensitive)	Public
Prepared By:	Helene Mihatsch, Robert Müllechner, Stefan Puschnigg (EIL – Energieinstitut an der JKU Linz)
Version:	1
Revised by:	Andreas Hawel, Jon Børgesen, Miguel Herrardor Moreno, Martin Kristiansen (ACSP – Aalborg CSP)

Disclaimer

This document's contents are not intended to replace the consultation of any applicable legal sources or the necessary advice of a legal expert, where appropriate. All information in this document is provided "as is" and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user, therefore, uses the information at its sole risk and liability. For the avoidance of all doubts, the European Commission has no liability in respect of this document, which is merely representing the authors' view.

Table of contents

1.	Executive summary	1
2.	Introduction	2
2.1	Background	2
2.2	Thermal energy storage systems	2
2.2.1	ATES	3
2.2.2	BTES	5
2.2.3	CTES	6
2.2.4	PTES	8
2.2.5	TTES	9
3.	Methods.....	10
3.1	Life cycle assessment.....	11
3.1.1	Definition of goal and scope.....	11
3.1.2	Life cycle inventory	14
3.1.3	Life cycle impact assessment.....	15
3.1.4	Interpretation	17
3.1.5	Land Use Value Calculation in Life Cycle Assessment (LANCA®)	17
3.2	PESTEL Analysis.....	18
3.3	Expert consultations	20
4.	Results of environmental implications	22
4.1	Results from preliminary LCA	22
4.2	Additional parameters from PESTEL analysis	24
4.2.1	Political factors	24
4.2.2	Economic factors	25
4.2.3	Social factors.....	26
4.2.4	Technological factors.....	26
4.2.5	Environmental factors	30
4.2.6	Legal factors.....	38
4.3	Results expert consultation	42
4.3.1	Soil	44
4.3.2	Water	45
4.3.3	Flora and fauna	46
4.3.4	Landscape	46
4.3.5	Resource use.....	47
4.3.6	Waste and deconstruction.....	48
4.3.7	Socio-ecological aspects	48
4.3.8	Open ended responses	49

5.	Discussion.....	50
5.1	Lessons learned for conducting LCAs for PTES	50
5.2	Indicators for environmental assessment from PESTEL analysis.....	52
5.3	Implications derived from Expert Consultations	55
5.3.1	Soil	55
5.3.2	Water	55
5.3.3	Flora and Fauna	55
5.3.4	Landscape	56
5.3.5	Resource use.....	56
5.3.6	Waste and deconstruction.....	56
5.3.7	Socio-ecological aspects	57
5.3.8	Air quality and climate, noise emission and light pollution.....	57
6.	Conclusion.....	58
7.	References.....	60
8.	Appendix.....	70
8.1	Questionnaire	70

List of figures

Figure 1: Schematic drawing of ATES	3
Figure 2: Schematic drawing of a BTES	6
Figure 3: Schematic drawing of a CTES	7
Figure 4: Schematic drawing of a PTES	8
Figure 5: Methodological approach to the environmental implications of PTES systems.....	10
Figure 6: The four phases of LCAs	11
Figure 7: Product System definition.....	13
Figure 8: Illustration of the LANCA model.....	17
Figure 9: PESTEL analysis.....	18
Figure 10: Network-like structure of interconnected parameters of a PESTEL analysis.....	19
Figure 11: System boundary, limitations and uncertainties	20
Figure 12: Excerpt from the survey addressing a first-level question on the negative impact of a PTES.....	21
Figure 13: Excerpt from the survey on a second-level question.....	22
Figure 14: Construction, operation, and EoL phase based on ISO 21930	23
Figure 15: Investment costs of TES systems	25
Figure 16: Diagrams of ground temperature sensors from Høje Taastrup.....	31
Figure 17: Side view of Høje Taastrup.....	32
Figure 18: Soil temperature measurements after quality control at Dronninglund	32
Figure 19: Long term ground temperature development of Marstal PTES	33
Figure 20: Survey results regarding the respondents' experience with PTES projects.....	42
Figure 21: Distribution of Responses on PTES Impact on Environmental Parameters	43
Figure 22: Graphical representation of ecological implication categories after PESTEL analysis	52

List of tables

Table 1: Overview of operating ATES systems	4
Table 2: Exemplary large BTES Systems	6
Table 3: CTES examples after	7
Table 4: Existing PTES systems according to literature	8
Table 5: Planned PTES projects	9
Table 6: impact assessment methods commonly used in LCA.....	15
Table 7: Overview of the different Impact Assessment Categories	16
Table 8: Water chemistry Dronninglund PTES	29
Table 9: Animal groups and their relationship	37
Table 10: National EIA Implication in the Demonstrator's Member States	41
Table 11: Soil – results from second-level environmental survey	44
Table 12: Water – results from second-level environmental survey	45
Table 13: Flora and fauna – results from second-level environmental survey	46
Table 14: Landscape – results from second-level environmental survey	47
Table 15: Resource use – results from second-level environmental survey.....	47
Table 16: Waste and deconstruction – results from second-level environmental survey.....	48
Table 17: Socio-ecological aspects – results from second-level environmental survey	48

Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

ATES	Aquifer thermal energy storage
BTES	Borehole thermal energy storage
CTES	Cavern thermal energy storage
CHP	Combined heat and power
DHN	District heating network
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EoL	End of Life
FU	Functional unit
GHG	Greenhouse gas
HDPE	High density polyethylene
HOB	Heat only boilers
LANCA®	Land use indicator value calculation in life cycle assessment
LCA	Life cycle assessment
LCI	Life cycle inventory
LTES	Large thermal energy storage
PESTEL	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental and Legal Analysis
PP	Polypropylene
PTES	Pit thermal energy storage
STES	Seasonal thermal energy storage
TES	Thermal energy storage
TTES	Tank thermal energy storage
WtE	Waste to energy

1. Executive summary

This executive summary outlines the relevant factors to assessing the environmental impacts of Pit Thermal Energy Storage (PTES) systems. It integrates findings from Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), additional environmental dimensions informed by a PESTEL-based analysis, and insights from expert consultations. The analysis highlights the main factors that shape the ecological performance of PTES across all life cycle stages and identifies challenges that should be accounted for. The summary provides guidance for conducting robust and comparable LCAs for PTES.

For conducting the LCA according to ISO 14040/44, the authors suggest the methodological framework of the ISO 21930 to enable reproducible assessment across different PTES. The product system is suggested to be divided into a construction, operation, and end-of-life phase. Operational impacts dominate the cumulative energy consumed throughout the lifetime of a PTES and thus require precise and accurate modeling during the life cycle inventory phase. This is especially the case for heat generation units, needed to charge the PTES. Allocation of environmental burdens to thermal energy outputs is essential, especially when PTES displaces CO₂-intensive technologies, as this substitution represents one of the largest ecological benefits for PTES. The relative significance of construction-phase impacts declines with higher energy throughput or displacement of CO₂-intensive heat. Land use is another critical factor and the LANCA[®] (Land Use Indicator Value Calculation) tool provides an established framework to quantify impacts on soil quality and ecosystem services. The functional unit definition is crucial for comparability. Therefore 1 MWh of delivered thermal energy transmitted through the PTES is suggested.

Insights from the PESTEL analysis highlight interconnected ecological considerations across political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal dimensions. Politically, PTES support district heating decarbonization. Economically, material selection influences both cost and environmental burdens. Social implications include social acceptance and interactions with culturally sensitive sites, although technical requirements often take precedence. Technologically, site selection and material longevity mitigate environmental risks. Environmentally, monitoring soil and groundwater quality is indispensable. Legally, regulations for groundwater warming and thermal impacts remain limited, emphasizing careful site selection.

The expert survey indicates that PTES generally has manageable environmental impacts, which are highly dependent on the site's conditions, project design, and size. Low impacts were reported for air, climate, noise, and light, while soil, water, flora and fauna, landscape, resource use, waste, and socio-ecological aspects can be moderate to high in specific subcategories. Proper assessment, monitoring, and site selection are key to minimizing potential negative effects.

Overall, PTES offers substantial potential for reducing greenhouse gas emissions in heat provision, particularly when displacing CO₂-intensive thermal energy, though careful consideration of construction impacts, emission allocation, and land use is essential. Systematic monitoring, robust lifecycle inventories, and attention to site-specific ecological conditions are key to ensuring sustainable deployment of PTES in decarbonized heating networks.

2. Introduction

Large Thermal Energy Storage (LTES) technologies (aquifer thermal energy storage - ATES, borehole thermal energy storage - BTES, cavern energy thermal storage - CTES, tank thermal energy storage - TTES, pit thermal storage - PTES) are central to integrating variable renewable heat and waste heat into district heating networks. This section provides background on the necessity and characteristics of LTES systems. PTES is cost effective for large seasonal storage but interacts strongly with land, soil, groundwater, and local ecosystems. This deliverable defines ecological implication parameters for PTES, provides a reproducible LCA framework, and supplies operational templates for demonstrators.

2.1 Background

When constructing and operating LTES systems, environmental aspects play an increasingly important role, as material choices, land use, and potential emissions can have long-term impacts on ecosystems and resources. Although the importance of these ecological factors is generally recognized, there is still a lack of comprehensive studies that systematically assess the environmental impacts of different LTES concepts. This research gap forms the background for the present work and highlights the need to consider environmental criteria early in the planning and development of such storage technologies.

Within the environmental assessment of this project, two main goals are to be fulfilled. First, the ecological implication parameters of large PTES need to be identified. This compilation of ecological implication parameters should provide future projects with a general, qualitative approach on assessing large PTES systems. Furthermore, it should provide a basis for LCA of PTES.

Since the ecological implications of PTES are influenced by a magnitude of parameters, learnings from existing similar TES systems should be incorporated as well, to establish an exhaustive description of the potential environmental impacts. A description and list of realized projects is included for each technology, without intending for the compendium to be complete. LTES projects are expanding rapidly globally with many projects yet to be officially announced.

2.2 Thermal energy storage systems

District heating networks (DHNs) supply thermal energy to consumers by circulating hot water through a pipe network. DHN can integrate thermal energy from various generation technologies such as biomass, waste incineration plants, combined heat and power plants (CHP), solar thermal energy, heat pumps, diverse waste heat sources, and electric boilers. This makes DHNs highly versatile. By integrating TES into DHN the heat demand and supply can be decoupled, adding to system stability and flexibility. Depending on the planned storage duration, short- or long-term storage is available. The focus of this study is on TES systems. TES can be categorized as sensible, latent and thermochemical systems. In sensible TES, energy is stored by applying a temperature gradient to a medium. This is the most developed and widely used heat storage technology. Due to its availability and environmental benignity, water is used predominantly as a storage medium (Zhao

et al., 2023). Furthermore, TES can be categorized based on their storage configuration, which includes ATES, BTES, CTES, TTES and most importantly for this study PTES. Another classification is based on the time frame for which the storage can offset demand and supply, distinguishing between hourly, daily, weekly or seasonal thermal energy storage. The latter can store excess heat during the summer months, when industrial waste heat and solar heat availability are high and heat demand is low. When the situation is reversed during the winter months, LTES can be discharged and balance the temporal heat demand and supply offset (Dahash et al., 2019b). This seasonal balancing can be achieved by integrating seasonal thermal energy storages (STES) into DHNs, which have a low cycle number (1–2).

2.2.1 ATES

ATES systems use groundwater as a long-term TES medium with an open-loop system by utilizing the groundwater’s high heat capacity and large volumes (Figure 1) (Stemmler et al., 2021). This technology is usually used for the thermal energy supply of large building complexes such as hospitals or office buildings, including cooling. A certain set of hydrogeological conditions, however, is required for the technology to be applicable such as permeable aquifer with low groundwater flow velocities.

FIGURE 1: SCHEMATIC DRAWING OF ATES (SOURCE: OWN ILLUSTRATION ENERGIEINSTITUT JKU LINZ)

The maximum temperatures for low-temperature ATES during charging are typically around 25 °C, for high-temperature ATES can reach temperatures above 40 °C (Fleuchaus et al., 2018; Stemmler et al., 2021). The depth of the system varies depending on the operated temperature regime (Lee, 2013). Low-temperature ATES systems use shallow aquifers, while high temperature aquifers operate at higher depths. Most systems in the Netherlands use aquifers between 20 and 150 m depth (Bloemendal and Beernik, 2020). An LCA study based on a regression model and Monte Carlo simulations found that the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions of ATES amount to 83 g CO_{2eq}/kWh_{th}. Compared to conventional systems fueled with oil, 74 % and compared

to natural gas 67 % of GHG emissions were saved (Stemmle et al., 2021). Commonly referenced ATES examples are referenced in (Table 1) and illustrate the variety of existing approaches.

TABLE 1: OVERVIEW OF OPERATING ATES SYSTEMS, A SELECTION CHOSEN BY (FLEUCHAUS ET AL., 2018)
*) CHARGE AND DISCHARGE CAPACITY

Location	Purpose	Year	Well depth [m]	Well number	Max. flow rate [m ³ /h]	Capacity ^{*)} [MW]	Reference
Amersfoort (NL)	Heating and cooling	1996	240	2	-	2	(Rosen and Koochi-Fayegh, 2017)
Oslo (NW)	Heating and cooling	1998	45	18	200	7	(Eggen and Vangnes, 2005)
Berlin (DE)	Heating and cooling	1999	60/300	12	100/300	-	(Sanner, 2003)
Rostock (DE)	heating	1999	20	2	15	-	(Schmidt and Müller-Steinhagen, 2004)
Amsterdam (NL)	Heating and cooling	2000	130	4	500	8.3	(IEA, 1998)
Brasschaat (BE)	Heating and cooling	2000	65	2	100	1.2	(Hoes et al., 2006)
Malmö (SW)	Heating and cooling	2001	75	10	120	1.3	(Andersson, 2007)
Mersin (TR)	cooling	2001	100	2	-	-	(Paksoy et al., 2004)
Agassiz (CA)	Heating and cooling	2002	60	5	40	0.563	(Bridger and Allen, 2010)
Eindhoven (NL)	Heating and cooling	2002	28-80	36	3000	20	(Snijders, 2005)
Malle ETAP (BE)	cooling	2003	67	2	90	0.6	(Hoes et al., 2006)
Neubrandenburg (DE)	heating	2005	1200	2	100	3.3	(Kabus et al., 2006)

New Jersey (US)	cooling	2008	60	6	272	2	(Paksoy et al., 2009)
Arlanda (SW)	Heating and cooling	2009	20	11	720	10	(Wigstrand, 2009)
Copenhagen (DK)	Heating and cooling	2009	-	2	-	2.4	(Balaji, 2025)
Malmö (SW)	Heating and cooling	2009	90	11	180	1.3	(Hellström, 2012)
Copenhagen (DK)	Heating and cooling	2010	100	10	250	2.8	(Fleuchaus et al., 2018)
Greenwich (UK)	Heating and cooling	2011	60	2	45	0.33	(Fleuchaus et al., 2018)
Shinshu (JP)	Heating and cooling	2011	50	5	-	-	(Tomigashi and Fujinawa, 2011)
London (UK)	Heating and cooling	2013	70	8	400	2.9	(Fleuchaus et al., 2018)
Amsterdam (NL)	Heating and cooling	2015	-	7	1100	20	(Fleuchaus et al., 2018)
Copenhagen (DK)	Heating and cooling	2015	110	10	-	5	(DTU International Energy Report 2015, 2015)

2.2.2 BTES

BTES use the underground rock or soil as a heat storage medium. Similar to ATEs systems, the heat is transferred via pipes (Figure 2). Because of the lower volumetric energy density compared to water, five times larger storage volumes are required for the same energy than hot water storages (Lüchinger et al., 2025). The feasibility of BTES systems is highly dependent on the underground conditions in the project area and special focus has to be put on the avoidance of groundwater heating and contamination (Sadeghi et al., 2024a). An exemplary list of realized BTES represented in literature can be found in Table 2.

FIGURE 2: SCHEMATIC DRAWING OF A BTES (SOURCE: OWN ILLUSTRATION ENERGIEINSTITUT JKU LINZ)

TABLE 2: EXEMPLARY LARGE BTES SYSTEMS

Country	BTES	Size	Capacity [MWh/a]	efficiency	Constructed in	Reference
Germany	Neckarsulm	528 boreholes 30 m deep	792	70 %	1999	(Nussbicker et al., 2006)
Alberta, Canada	Drake Landing Solar Community (DLSC)	144 boreholes 37 m deep covering 35,000 m ³	611	37 %	2007	(Mesquita et al., 2017)
Emmaboda, Sweden	Xylem	140 boreholes, 150m deep	3600	-	2010	(Nordell et al., 2015)
Stockholm, Sweden	Stockholm University	130 boreholes 230 m deep	3000	-	2015	(Monzó et al., 2016)

2.2.3 CTES

CTES systems utilize caverns in solid rocks as thermal energy storage facilities (Figure 3). This technology offers certain advantages, since it is characterized by an extremely long service life and almost invisible integration into the environment (Dahash et al., 2019b). One prominent CTES example is Varanto in Vantaa, Finland. This 90 GWh CTES with 1.1 million cubic meters water capacity and a maximum temperature of 140 °C is planned to start operation in 2030 (Vallin et al., 2025). Smaller CTES installations cited in (Gombert et al., 2019) are listed in Table 3.

FIGURE 3: SCHEMATIC DRAWING OF A CTES (SOURCE: OWN ILLUSTRATION ENERGIEINSTITUT JKU LINZ)

TABLE 3: CTES EXAMPLES AFTER (MÜLLER ET AL., 2026)

CTES	Sweden	Year	Use	Supply	Volume [m ³]	Capacity [MWh]	Reference
Avesta	Sweden	1980	Buffer, STES	Incineration Plant	15,000	750	(Rehbinder, 1988)
Lyckebo	Sweden	1982	STES	Incineration Plant	104,300	5500	(Brunstroem et al., 1986)
Oxelösund	Sweden	1988	STES	Waste heat	180,000	-	(Park et al., 2013)
Oulu	Finland	1997	Buffer, STES	Incineration Plant	190,000	8,000	(Lee, 2013; Sipilä and Ritola, 1990)
Hornsberg	Sweden	2010	Buffer (cooling)	CHP	55,000	400	(Gunasekara et al., 2021)
Vaasa	Finland	2020	Buffer	Incineration Plant	210,000	9,000	(Lieskoski et al., 2024)
Hudiksvall	Sweden	2020	Buffer	CHP	180,000	4,100	(MÅRTENSSON, 2020)
Mustikkamaa	Finland	2021	Buffer	CHP	260,000	11,600	(Lieskoski et al., 2024)
Västerås	Sweden	2024	Buffer	CHP	300,000	13,000	(Sagebrand et al., 2024)

2.2.4 PTES

PTES have been first implemented in the 1980s and are among the most cost-effective technologies for large-scale TES, especially in sub-urban and rural areas (Lüchinger et al., 2025; Sifnaios et al., 2023b). They essentially consist of excavated pits in the soil, which are lined with a waterproof polymer (Figure 4). Preferably the excavation is planned on a soil-balanced basis so that the excavated material can be reused to form the embankments. If geotechnical conditions preclude a soil-balance design, the PTES may be built above or as a (partially) submerged facility. The storage is filled with hot water and thermally isolated by the surrounding soil and by an insulated cover placed over the water surface. Thus, certain geological and hydrological prerequisites for PTES systems include ground stability and ideally the absence of groundwater (Bott et al., 2019). The size of reported PTES ranges from 1,500 to 200,000 m³, with most large PTES being located in Denmark. A list of operating PTES existing in literature can be found in Table 4. Furthermore, the planned PTES within the TREASURE project and one additional satellite PTES project (“Sonnenspeicher-Weitendorf”) are listed in Table 5.

FIGURE 4: SCHEMATIC DRAWING OF A PTES (SOURCE: OWN ILLUSTRATION ENERGIEINSTITUT JKU LINZ)

TABLE 4: EXISTING PTES SYSTEMS ACCORDING TO LITERATURE

Country	PTES	Volume [m ³]	Constructed in	Reference
Sweden	Studsvik	640	1978	(Heller, 1997)
Sweden	Lambohov	10,000	1980	(Hesaraki et al., 2015; Novo et al., 2010)
Germany	Stuttgart	1050	1986	(Hahne, 2000)
Sweden	Malung	3,000	1989	(Zinko and Hahn, 1994)
Denmark	Herlev (Tubberupvaenge)	3,000	1991	(Hesaraki et al., 2015)
Denmark	Ottrupgaard	1,500	1995	(Vang Jensen and Nielsen, 2020)
Germany	Jülich	2,500	1996	(Ochs et al., 2007)
Germany	Steinfurt-Borghorst	1,500	1998	(Schmidt et al., 2004)

Germany	Chemnitz	8000	2000	(Yang et al., 2021)
Germany	Eggenstein	4500	2008	(Ochs et al., 2008)
Denmark	Marstal	75,000	2012	(Jensen, 2014; Schmidt, 2019)
Croatia	Osijek	30,350	2013	(Dominković et al., 2015)
Denmark	Toftlund	70,000	2017	(Sifnaios, 2023)
Denmark	Dronninglund	60,000	2014	(Schmidt and Sørensen, 2018; Winterscheid and Schmidt, 2019)
Denmark	Gram	122,000	2015	(PlanEnergi, 2015)
Denmark	Vojens	200,000	2015	(Rambøll, 2015)
Denmark	Logumkloster	150,000	2016	(Radloff, 2015)
Tibet, China	Langkazi	15,000	2020	(Dubey, 2021)
Denmark	Høje-Taastrup	70,000	2023	(Sifnaios and Jensen, 2025)
Germany	Meldorf	43,000	2023	(Rambøll, 2023)
Poland	Lidzbark	15,000	2023	(TREASURE project, 2024)
Germany	Bracht	26,000	2025	(Solarwärme Bracht, 2025)

TABLE 5: PLANNED PTES PROJECTS

Country	PTES	Volume [m ³]	Planned operation	Reference
Germany	Hechingen	18,000	2027-2028	(TREASURE project, 2024)
Germany	Rostock	500,000	2027-2028	(TREASURE project, 2024)
Serbia	Pancevo	150,000	2027-2028	(TREASURE project, 2024)
Poland	Bytom	90,000	2027-2028	(TREASURE project, 2024)
Poland	Choszczno	30,000	2027-2028	(TREASURE project, 2024)
France	Pau	340,000	2027-2028	(TREASURE project, 2024)
Austria	Vienna	40,000	2027-2028	(TREASURE project, 2024), (Brunner et al., 2024)
Austria	Sonnenspeicher-Weitendorf	1,500,000	2027-2028	(Ammerer, 2024; Sonnenspeicher Süd, 2025)

2.2.5 TTES

TTES is a mature and widely applied technology for storing thermal energy. They are typically constructed of cylindrical steel tanks and filled with water as storage medium. TTES are widely used in DHNs and industrial processes, offering high efficiency and low operational complexity. Key aspects of TTES design include tank size, insulation quality and thermal stratification. The volumetric capacity ranges from small scale residential tanks (< 10 m³) to large scale applications with up to 80,000 m³ (IRENA, 2020). Due to the vertical subsurface construction, they differ significantly in their impact on their surroundings compared to the previously

mentioned LTES systems. Since the implications on the environment differ greatly from the effects of ATES, BTES, CTES and PTES systems, TTES are not covered further.

3. Methods

To provide a systematically analyzed compilation of the environmental implications linked to the planning, construction, and operation of a PTES system, different methods were applied. LCA (quantitative), PESTEL mapping (contextual indicators), and expert consultations (qualitative validation). The LCA follows ISO 14040/44 and adopts ISO 21930 modular stages to ensure reproducibility across demonstrators.

Figure 5 presents a graphical representation of the methodological approach. The basis for this approach is provided by the LCA framework. Literature research on LTES, and specifically PTES, has been conducted using the PESTEL method (PESTEL is an acronym for Political, Economic, Social, Technological, and Legal Analysis and will be elaborated in section 3.2). The participatory environmental assessment by experts from the TREASURE consortium, and external experts will serve as a further resource for the environmental implications of PTES. As a result, a collection of ecological parameters of PTES shall be derived.

FIGURE 5: METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH TO THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPLICATIONS OF PTES SYSTEMS (SOURCE: OWN ILLUSTRATION ENERGIEINSTITUT AN DER JKU LINZ)

3.1 Life cycle assessment

LCA is a well-established tool for assessing environmental impacts of products, services or processes throughout the entire life cycle. By examining every stage of production, use and waste management, LCA provides a holistic view of where environmental burdens occur. LCA helps companies, policymakers and researchers identify opportunities for improving sustainability and resource efficiency. Conducting the LCA relies on standardized procedures defined in the ISO 14040/14044 framework. It is performed in four phases: definition of goal and scope, the life cycle inventory (LCI), life cycle impact assessment and lastly the interpretation (Figure 6) (Finkbeiner et al., 2006).

FIGURE 6: THE FOUR PHASES OF LCAs AFTER (HAUSCHILD ET AL., 2018)

3.1.1 Definition of goal and scope

This study evaluates the cradle-to-grave ecological implications of PTES systems installed in district heating networks. During the definition of goal and scope the product system and its boundaries are defined. The product system refers to the collection of processes and activities that deliver the product's function. Its definition establishes the system boundaries, key assumptions and the level of detail required for the assessment. According to ISO 14040, the system boundary defines the unit processes to be included in the analysis. The selection of the elements of the physical system to be modeled is determined by the goal and scope of the study, its intended application and target audience, the assumptions made, the availability of data, cost constraints, and the applied allocation criteria (ISO 14040, 2006).

The system boundaries follow ISO 21930 and include:

- A1–A3: raw material extraction, manufacturing of components (liners, insulation, geotextiles, geonets, cassettes, gravel, piping)
- A4: transport to site.

- A5: installation, excavation, embankment construction, lid assembly.
- B1–B7: use phase, maintenance, repair, replacement, operational electricity and water, monitoring.
- C1–C4: deconstruction, transport to waste processing, waste processing, disposal.

Module D (benefits from reuse, recycling, and energy recovery) is reported separately as a sensitivity case.

The function of the PTES is to store thermal energy in times of low demand and to deliver it to the DHN in times of high demand. Thus, the geographical boundaries are defined by the extension of the DHN, the temporal boundaries are based on the lifetime of the PTES and are expected to range from 20 to 25 years (Schmidt et al., 2018; Sifnaios et al., 2023c). Depending on factors such as temperature, liner material, and insulation material, however, the lifetime may be longer. Therefore, the service life is closely linked to both the design and operational phases. The functional unit (FU) of thermal energy leaves the PTES and enters the DHN at the gate. This approach, however, considers the entire life cycle of the PTES construction from the procurement of raw materials to the discharge of thermal energy from the storage system into the DHN. The DHN itself is not included within the system boundary. However, any technologies required to adjust parameters such as temperature, pressure, etc. to enable integration into the DHN are considered within the system boundary. Additionally, the LCA considers the environmental impacts associated with the end-of-life (EoL) phase of the storage system, including landfilling or recycling. A simplified product system can be seen in Figure 7, categorized into three main phases, the manufacturing phase, operational phase and EoL phase.

FIGURE 7: PRODUCT SYSTEM DEFINITION (SOURCE: OWN ILLUSTRATION ENERGIEINSTITUT AN DER JKU LINZ)

To have a common basis for comparing alternative products or systems, a FU must be defined for the system. A clearly defined FU is essential for LCA, as it establishes the scope of the analysis and guides decisions about system boundaries and data collection. This way environmental impacts are assessed relative to the same delivered function and can be compared between different systems. Essentially, the FU can be understood as the numerator of the system, to which all inputs and outputs are normalized. For PTES product systems a suggested FU would be a unit of thermal energy provided to the DHN that was stored in a PTES intermediately (e.g. 1 MWh thermal energy).

Allocating burdens to different co-products of one process is a problem often encountered when conducting LCAs and should be defined in the goal and scope section. The ISO 14040/14044 framework prefers system expansion over allocation. System expansion, however, is often non-applicable due to a lack of precise data on the entire system. Furthermore, system expansion also requires the expansion of the FU by the additional benefit of the expanded system and thus the comparability with other (P)TES systems is severely limited. The generation of heat is often a co-product, next to power generation and thus a “fair” distribution of the burdens to power and heat will be necessary. These allocations can be based on physical factors such as exergy or energy, primary fuel input or economic factors (Buchenau et al., 2023; Famiglietti et al., 2021).

Limitations and uncertainties arise from the fact that, despite their technological advantages, seasonal PTES systems have been implemented in only a few cases so far. Thus, the results of the conducted LCA should

also help to mitigate negative environmental burdens and positively influence the planning phase of future PTES.

3.1.2 Life cycle inventory

The LCI is a compilation of all relevant data and calculations to quantify relevant inputs and outputs of the product system. This input data includes, but is not limited to, flows of energy, raw materials and ancillaries (Hauschild et al., 2018; Klöpffer and Grahl, 2014). Furthermore, co-products and waste flows as well as emissions to air, discharges to water bodies and to soil are considered.

A standardized bill of materials (BoM) is required for each demonstrator. The BoM must include supplier/product name, material type, density, thickness, and total quantities (m², m³, kg). Minimum required items:

- Floating liner (polymer type and grade).
- Geonet (HDPE).
- Geotextile (PP non-woven, g/m²).
- High-temperature PE insulation (e.g., Nomalén[®]).
- XPS insulation (product grade, e.g., XPS 300).
- Diffusion-open roof membrane (product name and g/m²).
- Ballast cassettes (material and mass per cassette).
- Gravel (size distribution and density).
- Manholes, air vents, pump wells (material and counts).
- Piping (material, diameter, length).

If supplier confidentiality prevents disclosure, anonymized EPDs or proxy datasets must be provided, together with a documented uncertainty factor.

This step is often the most critical for conducting an LCA as reliable results depend on high quality data. Databases like the ecoinvent 3.11 (Wernet et al., 2016) are applied to model foreground and background processes, as well as data derived from simulations, calculations and demonstration cases. Especially for technologies that are not commercially available yet or not fully mature, the data gaps need to be filled with data from existing literature and data based on assumptions.

3.1.3 Life cycle impact assessment

The Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) translates the LCI into environmental impact indicators relevant for PTES. Impact categories considered include global warming, ozone depletion and formation, toxicity impacts, particulate matter formation, ionizing radiation, acidification, eutrophication, land use and water use. The impact assessment evaluates the significance of the potential environmental impacts in different impact categories, which are specific to the different impact assessment methods.

Mathematically this is achieved by applying characterization factors for established impact categories on the results of the LCI. This is done along impact pathways towards midpoint or endpoint indicators. Midpoint indicators result in environmental impacts through substance emissions while endpoint categories result in different effects on human health, ecosystems or natural resource depletion (Hauschild et al., 2018). There are a multitude of different impact assessment methods available as can be seen in Table 6. They reflect different methodological approaches, regional applicability, time horizons and underlying assumptions for characterization models. The choice of method is context-sensitive and depends on the specific product system, to capture relevant impacts for a given product or application.

TABLE 6: IMPACT ASSESSMENT METHODS COMMONLY USED IN LCA

Impact Assessment Method	Impact Categories	Reference
IPCC AR6 (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change)	Climate Change – Global Warming Potential 20 years, 100 years	(Stocker et al., 2013)
ReCiPe (2016)	18 midpoint impact categories 3 endpoint areas of protection 20 years, 100 years, 1000 years	(Huijbregts et al., 2016)
TRACI (Tool for the Reduction and Assessment of Chemical and other Environmental Impacts)	9 impact categories 100 years	(Bare, 2011)
EF (Environmental Footprint)	16 impact categories single score (by weighting and normalization) 100 years	(Andreasi Bassi et al., 2023)

Depending on the defined goal and scope of the LCA, different impact categories can be relevant. Thus, different impact assessment methods can be facilitated for different studies. A brief overview of established methods and their impact categories can be found in Table 7.

TABLE 7: OVERVIEW OF THE DIFFERENT IMPACT ASSESSMENT CATEGORIES WITHIN THE IMPACT ASSESSMENT METHODS, (+) INDICATE THAT THE CATEGORY IS AVAILABLE FOR THIS METHOD, BLANK FIELDS INDICATE THAT THESE CATEGORIES ARE UNAVAILABLE FOR SAID METHOD

Impact assessment categories	IPCC (2021)	ReCiPe (2016)	TRACI	EF 3.1
Global Warming	+	+	+	+
Climate Change: biogenic GWP 100	+			
Climate Change: biogenic emissions GWP 100	+			
Climate Change: (incl. biogenic CO ₂) total GWP 100	+			
Climate Change: total (incl. biogenic CO ₂ inc. SLCFs) GWP 100	+			
Stratospheric ozone depletion		+	+	+
Tropospheric ozone formation (human)		+		
Tropospheric ozone formation (ecosystem)		+		
Human toxicity cancer		+	+	+
Human toxicity non-cancer		+	+	+
Particulate matter		+	+	+
Smog formation			+	
Ionizing radiation		+		+
Photochemical ozone formation				+
Acidification		+	+	+
Eutrophication		+	+	+
Freshwater eutrophication		+		+
Terrestrial eutrophication				+
Marine eutrophication				+
Ecotoxicity		+	+	+
Terrestrial ecotoxicity		+		
Marine ecotoxicity		+		
Land use		+		+
Water use		+		+
mineral resources		+		+
fossil resources		+		+

3.1.4 Interpretation

Finally, the results of the impact assessment are interpreted within the goal and scope of the LCA. Interpretation can be done either by comparing different technologies (PTES with another LTES system), different PTES projects, or by comparing the PTES system with the business-as-usual case. LCA is an iterative method, leading to many iterations through the phases until sufficiently accurate and precise results can be achieved. Depending on the goal and scope of the study, a sensitivity analysis, validations and consistency checks are in order before the final conclusions can be derived.

3.1.5 Land Use Value Calculation in Life Cycle Assessment (LANCA®)

Land is a limited resource, resulting in competition between different land use practices and their consequences for the quality of the land. Many methods have been published which can be used to model environmental impacts of land use. There are essentially two approaches for quantifying land use: the first focusing on biodiversity, the second on quantification of soil functionality. Because data on soil function is generally more accessible and simpler for data collection, the second approach is considered to be more applicable (Beck et al., 2010). For PTES projects where data on the soil needs to be collected to perform geotechnical analysis, this approach appears especially suitable.

FIGURE 8: ILLUSTRATION OF THE LANCA MODEL FROM (HORN ET AL., 2021)

As a calculation tool, LANCA systematically and quantitatively captures land use and its effects. LCIA results are reported per functional unit and, where appropriate, per area of land (transformation) and per area and time unit of land (occupation) to facilitate interpretation of LANCA outputs.

The framework is based on elementary flows for occupation of land [m²a] and for transformation of land from one land use type to another [m²]. This means the input for the model consists of the land use type, the location, the duration of the land use, and the area. With these input flows land use impacts are calculated, using characterization factors on country level (or site-specific data if available) for various land use types. As

a midpoint result, characterized results for all LANCA indicators are available. These include erosion resistance, physio-chemical filtration, groundwater regeneration, mechanical filtration and soil organic carbon. As a further result, normalization and aggregation can be performed to deliver a single, dimensionless Soil Quality Index (Beck et al., 2010) (Figure 8). LANCA is based on the UNEP-SETAC guideline on global land use impact assessment on biodiversity and ecosystem services in LCA and as such serves as a powerful tool to enhance the results of LCA (Koellner et al., 2013).

3.2 PESTEL Analysis

PESTEL is an acronym based on the **political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal** contributing factors. It is a tool originally developed for management framework and diagnostic analysis, which aids in understanding external factors that impact strategies and business decisions. Utilizing the PESTEL framework enables a holistic approach, with particular emphasis placed on ecological factors within the context of this study's objective (Olayiwola et al., 2025).

FIGURE 9: PESTEL ANALYSIS (SEGURA ET AL., 2023)

The PESTEL framework was chosen because it provides a systematic and comprehensive approach to ensure that all aspects potentially affecting the environmental performance of PTES are considered, especially those that are not considered within the LCA framework. By examining political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal factors, the analysis helps to systematically identify both obvious and less apparent drivers that could influence environmental outcomes throughout the planning, construction and operational phases. This is particularly valuable for PTES, where interactions with regulatory frameworks, community acceptance, technological developments, market-conditions and site-specific environmental constraints have significant or indirect impacts. Using PESTEL ensures that no critical factor is overlooked, supporting holistic assessment that informs more sustainable design, decision-making and long-term operation (Figure 9).

The first step to performing a PESTEL analysis is the definition of a system boundary and scope and is done in accordance with the LCA framework. This includes the geographical scope and the time horizon. As a next step relevant factors for each PESTEL dimensions are identified via literature research. Since only a limited number of seasonal PTES are currently in operation, findings from alternative TES systems such as ATES, BTES and CTES are also considered. The findings are compiled in this document and insights that inform strategic, operational or environmental decision-making are emphasized. The next step in conducting PESTEL analysis includes the assessment and prioritization of the identified factors within each PESTEL analysis and is done by expert consultations within the project consortium and external experts.

Since this model is chosen to provide a holistic view of the environment implications related to PTES projects, the pillars of the PESTEL dimensions are intertwined. For example, environmental regulations and legal requirements are connected to each other, as well as raw material costs and technological innovations (e.g. for the required lid of the PTES system). This network-like connection of parameters is illustrated in a generalized way in Figure 10.

FIGURE 10: NETWORK-LIKE STRUCTURE OF INTERCONNECTED PARAMETERS OF A PESTEL ANALYSIS AFTER (HO, 2014)

Limitations of the systems under study mainly arise from the limited number of PTES that exist today. Although PTES is a promising technique to help decarbonize DHNs, the technology is not widely applied yet, especially for STES application (Sifnaios et al., 2023c). Further limitations that affect the environmental implications of PTES systems are due to research gaps in the research area of groundwater quality and soil quality due to heat sources in the ground. Uncertainties also arise from energy demand during construction and operation as well as uncertainties connected to material properties (Sadeghi et al., 2024b) (Figure 11). Findings of similar research fields, like the effect of global warming on soil and groundwater was included, if considered to be similar to PTES systems.

FIGURE 11: SYSTEM BOUNDARY, LIMITATIONS AND UNCERTAINTIES

3.3 Expert consultations

Based on a literature review focusing on the identification and description of environmentally relevant parameters of LTES, including PTES, an expert survey was developed. The objective of the survey was to validate the environmental parameters identified in the literature and to quantitatively assess their potential negative impacts. The survey serves as a preparatory step for a subsequent LCA and therefore explicitly focuses on identifying potential environmental burdens. Positive impacts of PTES projects were not considered and were outside the scope of this survey.

The survey was distributed to 21 experts involved in the TREASURE project, of whom 16 returned complete questionnaires. Experts were selected based on their professional involvement in TREASURE. The survey was conducted online between the 2nd and 18th of December 2025 using the tool SurveyEngine. Experts were contacted directly via email. To identify duplicate responses, email addresses were collected, meaning that the survey was formally non-anonymous, according to the developed data protection plan.

To contextualize the level of expertise of the participants, the survey began with the question “What experience do you have with PTES projects?”. Multiple answers were allowed, as many experts possess diverse experience profiles. The queried categories included direct involvement in the implementation of a PTES project, participation in PTES feasibility studies, long-term work on PTES-related topics without direct project implementation, research activities, and no prior experience with PTES projects.

The questionnaire followed a two-level structure and focused on assessing the negative impacts of PTES projects on selected environmental parameters. The evaluated parameters included soil, water, air and climate, flora and fauna, landscape, resource use, waste and deconstruction, noise emissions, socio-ecological aspects, and light pollution.

In the first level, these environmental parameters were queried in a general manner without addressing specific details, as exemplarily shown in Figure 12. Experts were asked to assess the negative impact of a PTES project on each parameter using a five-point Likert scale, which is an established evaluation framework for surveys. The value of one indicated a low negative impact, the value of five indicated a high negative impact. The five-point scale was chosen to enable quantitative analysis as well as to ensure practicality and comparability with similar studies.

Category: Soil

(sealing, contamination, quality)

How significantly could a PTES project negatively impact soil resources?

Impact (1 low – 5 high)

Select only one answer

1	2	3	4	5
<input type="radio"/>				

FIGURE 12: EXCERPT FROM THE SURVEY ADDRESSING A FIRST-LEVEL QUESTION ON THE NEGATIVE IMPACT OF A PTES PROJECT ON THE ENVIRONMENTAL PARAMETER SOIL.

Following the first level, an open-ended question was included to allow experts to indicate whether any relevant ecological parameters were missing or insufficiently addressed.

If a parameter received a rating of ≥ 3 , additional, more detailed questions were presented in a second level. The threshold of three was selected as it represents at least a moderate negative impact and therefore indicates the need for further examination. The purpose of the second level was to identify specific aspects of the environmental parameters that may be negatively affected by PTES projects. An excerpt of the questions in the second level is exemplarily shown in Figure 13.

Category: Soil

Since you previously rated soil as a highly influential ecological factor, please describe how a PTES project could negatively affect the sub-categories listed below.

Impact (1 low – 5 high)

Select one response from each row

	1	2	3	4	5
Sealing & compaction	<input type="radio"/>				
Excavation & contamination	<input type="radio"/>				
Quality (warming, pH, moisture, (bio)chemistry)	<input type="radio"/>				

FIGURE 13: EXCERPT FROM THE SURVEY ON A SECOND-LEVEL QUESTION CONCERNING THE NEGATIVE IMPACTS OF A PTES PROJECT ON CERTAIN SOIL PROPERTIES.

After completion of the second level, an additional open-ended question was included to collect further comments, feedback, or suggestions. The responses to open-ended questions were evaluated in a supplementary manner and are qualitatively discussed in the results section.

4. Results of environmental implications

This chapter explores the ecological implications of PTES. It considers political, economic, social, environmental, and legal factors to understand the broader consequences of PTES deployment.

4.1 Results from preliminary LCA

Preliminary results from LCA on TES are presented in this section to serve as a basis to conduct the more detailed LCAs of the specific demonstrators in the TREASURE project. These preliminary assessments provide insight into potential environmental impacts across different TES systems and highlight key processes and materials that may drive the overall environmental performance.

In order to rely on a systematic approach during the LCI phase, the ISO 21930 is applied (ISO 21930, 2017). This approach helps to systematically go through each demonstrator, without missing necessary steps during the construction, operation, and EoL phase. Following the ISO 21930 guideline also helps to ensure comparability between the demonstrators. The methodological framework was designed for attributional LCAs and is based on the modularity principle. Furthermore, a polluter-pays principle is applied, which is especially relevant for the EoL phase. In order to account for the different service lifetimes of all used components, a reference service life is introduced. This is the service life of a construction product under a

set of reference in-use conditions, which is especially relevant for PTES applications, where components must sustain elevated temperatures ($>80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) for long periods of time (> 20 years).

The structure of the ISO 21930 was then adapted to the life phases defined in the goal and scope definition: construction (phase A), operation (phase B), and EoL (phase C), as can be seen in Figure 14.

FIGURE 14: CONSTRUCTION, OPERATION, AND EOL PHASE BASED ON ISO 21930

Main components for the construction phase include the lid and the liner material. The material composition of the lid and the liner require extensive understanding of the raw material extraction, material production, and assembly. Since these constructive components are innovative and have not found broad application yet, the related processes and their inputs need to be modeled in an LCA software in detail to fully capture the environmental impacts. The liner material can be made of polymers such as polypropylene or polyethylene and is fabricated into foils, which are then welded in place. The lid, which serves an insulating function for the PTES, can be made of different polymers and the implementation can range from simply covering the water surface while insulating to fully load-bearing structures (Sørensen et al., 2023). The exact set-up and composition have to be evaluated for each demonstrator and will be modeled accordingly.

During the operational phase, the heat generation units must be defined precisely within the model. This includes all units that provide energy for the DHN such as Waste-to-Energy (WtE), biomass, CHP, Heat-Only-Boilers (HOB), solar thermal energy, power to heat, industrial waste heat, heat pumps and electric boilers.

The electricity required for operating heat pumps or other post-heating equipment must be considered, along with the energy demand for auxiliary components such as submersible pumps and water-treatment systems. This can also include the development of different scenarios for charging the storage depending on the location of the PTES and development of the DHN. Important parameters that need to be defined for the operational phase are the cycle number of the storage, which defines the number of times the storage is completely charged and discharged throughout one year of operation. The cycle number not only reflects the amount of energy that a TES provides in one year, but it also has significant influence on how the generation units are dispatched. High cycle numbers for short-term TES are typically to buffer daily or weekly discrepancies in heat demand and generation. Seasonal thermal storages with low cycle numbers can help to provide heat during winter months that was stored as excess heat during the summer.

Lastly, the EoL phase needs to be considered. This includes processes like dismantling or renaturation, waste management, and potential recyclability of components or possible reuse of components.

Within the TREASURE project different demonstrators are studied which vary in storage capacity, constructional execution and charging. The influence of these differences on the impact assessment can be studied in greater detail based on the demonstrator-specific data.

4.2 Additional parameters from PESTEL analysis

In this section the dimensions of the PESTEL analysis will be listed and subcategories derived from relevant literature will be described. This method serves as a systematic approach to cover all aspects relevant to the environmental effects of the implementation of PTES, especially those that might not be covered by LCA.

4.2.1 Political factors

The ambitious goal of the European Green Deal to make the EU the first climate-neutral continent in the world by 2050 requires drastic changes in the energy sector (European Commission, 2019). This should, among other strategies, be fulfilled by implementing 42.5 % of the energy consumed in the EU from renewable sources. Especially in the building sector this calls for the integration of TES systems (Directive (EU) 2023/2413, 2023). The European Commission highlights energy system flexibility as a key goal, including DHNs. By converting surplus electricity into heat through sector coupling, DHNs can balance the power grid, integrate variable renewable electricity, and provide cost-effective system integration solutions. Particularly energy storage technologies such as LTES in DHNs can provide stability and reliability (*Commission Recommendation of 14 March 2023 on Energy Storage – Underpinning a decarbonised and secure EU energy system 2023/C 103/01*, 2023). Additionally, LTES can facilitate the integration of renewable heating and cooling resources for DHN. These include shallow geothermal, solar thermal and ambient energy technologies. This is essential to shift towards a fossil-free heating system in the building sector (*Commission Recommendation of 14 March 2023 on Energy Storage – Underpinning a decarbonised and secure EU energy system 2023/C 103/01*, 2023).

Several industry associations and interest groups actively promote the wider deployment of TES within DHNs. These organizations represent the interests of technology providers, utilities, policymakers, and research institutions, and aim to create favorable framework conditions for large-scale storage integration. They advocate supportive regulations, investment incentives, and long-term energy strategies that recognize the role of storage in increasing system flexibility, enhancing the use of renewable heat, and improving overall energy efficiency. Through communication, lobbying activities, stakeholder coordination, and dissemination of best practices, these interest groups contribute to raising awareness and accelerating the adoption of TES technologies in DHNs.

4.2.2 Economic factors

The economic factors stated in PESTEL analysis can often be classified into the factors business cycles, interest rates, exchange rates, inflation rates, economic growth, raw material costs and tariffs (Olayiwola et al., 2025). For the assessment of the ecological implications, it is determined that the PTES is already considered to be economically feasible. PTES systems surpassing 10,000 MWh are estimated to be substantially cheaper than ATES, BTES and TTES systems (Sadeghi et al., 2024b; Worm, 2017) (Figure 15).

FIGURE 15: INVESTMENT COSTS OF TES SYSTEMS (SADEGHI ET AL., 2024; WORM, 2017)

Direct implications on the environment derived from economic factors can be the material selection for the liner materials and insulating materials in the lids. This is due to the fact that certain materials, although technically applicable, cannot be utilized due to their high costs (e.g. steel lining instead of polymers).

Furthermore, the degree of monitoring needed for the PTES, including the deployment of temperature and humidity sensors, influences both the environmental footprint and the overall feasibility of the project.

4.2.3 Social factors

Social factors relevant for environmental implications are based on the characteristics of the area, the location of settlements, their functional interrelationships, central facilities, social infrastructure, leisure and recreational facilities as well as cultural heritage (Directive 2014/52/EU, 2014; Eberhartinger-Tafill, 2019).

Especially health consciousness is an important social factor when it comes to projects that have the potential to negatively impact the drinking water or water resources used for other purposes (like irrigation). These topics are further covered in section 4.2.5.1.

Cultural heritage is also an important aspect of environmental assessments within the social dimension, as construction projects can affect the accessibility, integrity, or perception of cultural facilities and monuments. However, in the case of PTES projects, cultural heritage considerations are typically not expected to play a central role in environmental evaluation. These facilities are usually planned in peripheral or industrial areas, away from major cultural institutions. This generally reduces the chance of significant interactions or adverse effects. However, some aspects of heritage may still be present within the project site.

Social acceptance plays an important role for realizing energy projects, including factors such as visual impact or aesthetics (Enserink et al., 2022). Studies also found that benefit perception matters more than objective risk management, as people tend to accept energy solutions if they believe the benefits (cost savings, environmental protection, reliability) outweigh the risk or inconveniences (Milani et al., 2024). However, general acceptance cannot be equated with local acceptance. Even if people support energy transformations in general, the acceptance often decreases when installations are planned near their homes (Baur et al., 2022). Successful and time-efficient transition towards a more sustainable energy system thus requires public support (Bevk and Golobič, 2020; Sütterlin and Siegrist, 2017).

Further information related to social factors can be found in TREASURE Deliverable 6.3 focusing on non-market benefits of PTES and in the Task 6.3 focusing on social acceptance.

4.2.4 Technological factors

The following section provides the findings of the PESTEL analysis within the technological dimension based on literature available for installed PTES systems.

Although PTES systems are promising LTES solutions for cost- and energy-efficient contributions to the DHNs, the technology has not found wide application yet in European context. The technological development of PTES and the momentum for their implementation have only significantly increased over the past 10 to 15 years (Sifnaios et al., 2023c) (also see Table 4).

The choice of the location of a PTES naturally has direct consequences on its environmental impacts as well as its technical feasibility. Of course, the connecting pipe lengths to an existing DHN should be kept minimal, while enough area needs to be available for the construction of an PTES. It can be expected that the distances between the PTES and DHN need to be relatively short. While literature reports economically feasible distances ranging from 15 km to 87 km (Kapil et al., 2012; Scholliers et al., 2024), the linear distances for constructed PTES are much shorter (< 3 km) according to experts. From a technical point of view, the location is also of utmost importance to avoid areas of shallow groundwater bodies, as this reduces the PTES' efficiency. For example, fast flowing groundwater bodies lower the efficiency of PTES systems by 15 %, whereas for TTES systems the efficiency is lowered by only 8 % (Sifnaios et al., 2023b).

This is also the case for high soil thermal conductivity due to a water-saturation (Dahash et al., 2019a; Sifnaios et al., 2023b). Thus, a thorough examination of the groundwater body in the entire construction area is necessary, also given the fact that this mitigates the risk of quantitative or qualitative impairment. Changes related to the groundwater body that are associated with high intensities of ecological implications should best already be considered in the planning phase. These include the drawdown or mounding of the groundwater table, localized or regional changes in groundwater availability, or general or partial modification of the physio-chemical water quality due to lubricants or operating supplies (Eberhartinger-Tafill, 2019).

4.2.4.1 Material choice

The materials that are used in a PTES system must fulfill a set of technical requirements, such as temperature and chemical stability, long lifetimes and they need to be easily installed at the construction site. These material choices lead to ecological implications based on the raw materials needed for production and manufacturing as well as resource efficiency. In the following section the materials needed for the construction of PTES are discussed based on literature of installed PTES.

Liners and Water Losses

The liner is a critical element in PTES, as it ensures water tightness, protects insulation, and influences both heat retention and water losses (Schmidt et al., 2018; Xiang et al., 2022). Historically, stainless steel liners were used, but polymer liners have become more common due to lower costs and simpler installation. Materials such as high-density polyethylene (HDPE) and polypropylene (PP) are applied. However, a major challenge is the water vapor permeability, which increases strongly with temperature:

- **HDPE:** approx. 0.03 g/m²day at 20 °C (1 mm thickness), approx. 1.5 g/m²day at 80 °C (2.5 mm thickness).
- **PP:** about four times higher than HDPE.
- **LDPE and PVC:** up to 45–115 times higher than HDPE (Schmidt et al., 2018; Xiang et al., 2022).

For the construction of the Høje Taastrup for example PTES, PP liners were used. Different technical lifetimes have been reported for the latter. The Danish Technological Institute reported lifetimes of only up to 6 years at 90 °C, whereas RISE (Swedish accredited testing institution) reported up to 25 years (Sørensen *et al.* (2023)). Polypropylene liners (PP) can show even higher technical lifetimes of 20 - 47 years at 95 °C, based on laboratory experiments, the supplier does not guarantee this lifetime, however (Sørensen *et al.*, 2023). The lifetime of the used polymers naturally affects the magnitude of the environmental burdens connected to the construction of a PTES.

Lid Construction and Corrosion Protection

Lids need to be designed to adapt to water level variations. Floating lids with embedded insulation help to prevent air gaps between water and the lid, as the construction adapts to the rising or sinking water surface. This design has been applied in Danish PTES systems (Schmidt *et al.*, 2018; Sifnaios *et al.*, 2023a).

Service Life

From the Dronninglund PTES (see Table 4), one lesson learned is that the environmental implications relate to the material used for insulation. The construction was officially completed in 2014 but due to the lid being damaged beyond feasible repair it had to be modified in 2022 (Sifnaios *et al.*, 2023a). This shows that the selection of long-lasting insulating material is essential for reducing the environmental burden connected to the PTES construction phase. Material selection is mainly affected by the temperature level intended for the PTES. As long as maximum water temperatures of 90 °C are intended there are polymer solutions available that sustain these temperatures for at least 20 years, like HDPE (Sifnaios *et al.*, 2023a).

4.2.4.2 Water quality and water losses in PTES

Water quality is crucial for the durability and performance of PTES, since many components such as pipes, pumps, heat exchangers, and steel liners are in direct contact with the storage water. To prevent corrosion, treated district heating water is generally used. This water is desalinated, softened, dechlorinated, and deoxygenated. Typical requirements are: hardness <0.1 °dH, conductivity <130 µS/cm, iron <0.005 mg/l, oxygen <20 µg/l, and a pH value of around 9.8, which is maintained by adding sodium hydroxide (Sifnaios *et al.*, 2023a; Vang Jensen and Nielsen, 2020). The measured parameters on the water chemistry for the Dronninglund PTES can be found in Table 8.

TABLE 8: WATER CHEMISTRY DRONNINGLUND PTES

parameter	value	unit
hardness	< 0.1	°dH
conductivity	130	µS/cm
Iron content	< 0.005	mg/L
oxygen content	< 20	µg/L
pH	9.8 ± 0.2	

If soil particles or impurities enter the storage during filling, they may cause bacterial corrosion or clogging of heat exchangers. The optimal pH depends on the materials used: steel requires higher pH levels to reduce corrosion, whereas aluminum components corrode already at pH >8 (Vang Jensen and Nielsen, 2020). Regular monitoring and adjustment of water chemistry are therefore essential (Sifnaios et al., 2023a).

4.2.4.3 Reuse of material during construction

A measure relevant to the economical, technological and environmental pillar of the PESTEL analysis is the reuse of excavated soil from the pit to form the embankment. This can reduce the emissions related to transport and reduce expenditure if the material is environmentally benign (enough). Soil and excavation material thus needs to be chemically analyzed. Reusing the excavated soil for the embankments has been successfully implemented for the Høje Taastrup PTES system by designing the geometry of the PTES with the goal of soil balance (Sørensen et al., 2023). If soil balance is not possible due to site-specific restriction, the transport of the excavated material to a landfill and the transport of the embankment to the site can have further transport-related environmental impacts (dust emission, noise emissions and carbon dioxide emission due to heavy-duty vehicles). Consequently, the construction related changes in traffic possibly need to be studied. This includes the frequency and amount of transported excavation material and which infrastructure can be used to do so (Eberhartinger-Tafill, 2019). This is also applicable to other means of transport necessary during the construction phase.

4.2.5 Environmental factors

This section covers environmental factors related to groundwater and soil quality, temperature changes in groundwater and soil as well as flora, fauna and habitat aspects that can be affected by PTES. Lastly, effects on the climate and direct emissions are discussed.

4.2.5.1 Long-term ground temperature changes

Variations in ground and soil temperature can significantly impact both fauna and flora, necessitating comprehensive research to evaluate their environmental consequences. There are different trends discussed in literature, when it comes to elevated soil temperatures and microbial activity (Billings and Ballantyne IV, 2013; Streit et al., 2014). Warmer soil leads to an increased activity in soil microbes, which then increases carbon respiration, which then decreases the easily available soil organic carbon pool, essentially decreasing an easily available carbon source for microbes. Because of that, ancient carbon stored in the soil is broken down by the microbes instead, decreasing the soil's health long-term. This ultimately leads to a slowed down activity in microbial activity (Schindlbacher et al., 2011). Short term temperature increases of 3-4 years usually lead to bacterial adjustment to higher temperatures. Longer changes in temperature reduce their activity. Also, higher temperatures can lead to a reduction in growth efficiency. Another opposite effect is based on the moisture content and carbon movement. While warmer soil is more moist, which hinders the microbes access to carbon, the carbon movement gets easier in warmer temperatures (Zhang et al., 2023).

Temperature changes in the soil are of scientific interest, since increasing temperatures are estimated to occur due to climate change, even if there are no additional warming activities like PTES in place. It is projected that indirect effects of temperature increase on carbon balance are more important than direct effects (Shaver et al., 2000). This relates, for example, to reduced nutrient availability or as already mentioned in connection with microbial conditions, to drier soil conditions. Consequences are a potential decrease in diversity (Fang et al., 2021). Ultimately, this affects the species competitive interactions, the activity of herbivores and pathogens, leading to changes in water and nutrient limitations with complex long-term effects on carbon turnover, net primary production (input of carbon to the ecosystem) and heterotrophic respiration (loss of carbon from the ecosystem) (Herbert et al., 1999; Shaver et al., 2000). Higher ground temperature also contributes to lower pH and moisture content and chemistry imbalance, hence causing restriction for regeneration of vegetation (Nishar et al., 2017).

Special concern related to ground stability is advised in cold climate regions. Increasing ground temperature in these areas could result in thawing ice lenses or permafrost soil. This can reduce ice-cementation bonds between soil particles and induce wet-mass movements such as debris flow and other related instabilities (Chang et al., 2019). For example, the pile-bearing capacity can be reduced by a factor of 3 when temperatures increase from -3 °C to 3 °C (Kudryavtsev et al., 2021).

This short comparison of partially opposite effects and their consequences should indicate that it is not generally possible to state how thermal energy input into the soil affects the microbial environment

surrounding PTES systems. Therefore, site-specific studies based on temperature, moisture and microbial activity around a PTES would be necessary to assess the individual effects.

4.2.5.2 Case studies on temperature changes

The Høje Taastrup PTES was constructed started operating in 2023 and feeds into the DHN of Copenhagen with a volume of 70,000 m³ (Table 4) and an operating temperature of max. 90 °C. Sensors installed for the monitoring system included water temperature, storage water level, lid conditions (humidity and heat flux), ground temperature, ambient conditions (air temperature, wind speed and humidity), diffuser temperature and flow rate as well as charged/discharged energy.

FIGURE 16: DIAGRAMS OF GROUND TEMPERATURE SENSORS FROM HØJE TAASTRUP WITH DATA FROM SIFNAIOS ET AL., (2025)

The ground temperature was measured by 11 temperature sensors buried in the embankment, with a 4 m distance from the water edge. Each sensor is approx. 1.4 m apart in vertical direction. As can be seen from Figure 16, the shallower temperature sensors up to 2.69 m depth show a different temperature curve throughout the year than the deeper sensors, getting less coupled to ambient temperature changes the further down the sensor is. While seasonal changes in ground temperature at that depth are not visible anymore, there is a steady temperature increase throughout the monitored operation time. It shall be added here that due to the truncated pyramid shape of the PTES (Figure 17) and due to the temperature gradient of the water (warmer water on top, colder further down), the temperature sensors that are installed vertically are not directly comparable.

FIGURE 17: SIDE VIEW OF HØJE TAASTRUP (SIFNAIOS ET AL., 2025)

A similar behavior can be seen for the monitoring data available for the Dronninglund PTES (Figure 18) (Sifnaios et al., 2023a), where the near-surface measurement points show a far greater temperature variation than the sensors that are beyond 20 m depth.

FIGURE 18: SOIL TEMPERATURE MEASUREMENTS AFTER QUALITY CONTROL AT DRONNINGLUND (SIFNAIOS ET AL., 2023A)

Furthermore, long-term ground temperature data from the Marstal PTES is available (Schmidt and Sørensen, 2018). Temperature increases in 18 m depth of more than 5 °C are observed, where near-surface changes show seasonal surface temperature changes (Figure 19). For this case, similar to the data from Høje Taastrup PTES, a steady temperature increase is observable in larger depths throughout the monitored time of operation.

Especially in the presence of groundwater, and even more so for high flow rates, the efficiency of the PTES can decrease dramatically, leading to a heat loss increase of up to 15 % (Dahash et al., 2019a). This indicates that beyond the environmental concerns related to elevated groundwater temperatures, also from a technical perspective the avoidance of groundwater saturated zones within the project area is beneficial.

FIGURE 19: LONG TERM GROUND TEMPERATURE DEVELOPMENT OF MARSTAL PTES FROM (SCHMIDT AND SØRENSEN, 2018)

4.2.5.3 Soil quality changes

Soil quality is a fundamental determinant of ecosystem health, influencing water retention, nutrient cycling and vegetation growth (Smith et al., 2015). The soil quality changes due to the realization of a PTES project have to be assessed based on soil geology, the current land use, and the description of soil types based on available maps or surveys. Accordingly, knowledge of ecological soil functions is necessary to assess the potential impacts correctly. This includes the description of any older deposits or designated contaminated areas within the project area. Furthermore, national regulation on land consumption need to be taken in consideration (Eberhartinger-Tafill, 2019).

Due to the technical necessities, vulnerable areas are not taken into consideration for PTES locations, such as wetlands, moors or floodplains. Furthermore, contaminated areas are most likely to be avoided to reduce costs during excavation and to be able to build PTES as a soil balanced concept. Effects caused by altering existing soils, in particular through terrain correction, are considered to have considerable ecological effects. The compaction of soil increases its density and strength, but decreases the porosity, soil hydraulic conductivity, and nutrient availability, thus reducing the soil’s overall health (Shah et al., 2017). Generally, the compaction of soil and the increase of land take is closely related to increased flood risks (Wheater and Evans, 2009). Consequently, this needs to be assessed based on the soil’s condition prior to construction.

Mitigation strategies such as temporary revegetation of the excavated soil to reduce wind erosion and loss of available water in the soil, and the erection of compensation areas can help to mitigate the negative impacts.

4.2.5.4 Groundwater warming and groundwater quality changes

Protecting groundwater resources is critical because it safeguards drinking water, preserves aquatic ecosystems, and supports agricultural and industrial activities that depend on reliable water availability. Despite consensus within the scientific community on the importance of groundwater quality, the resulting impacts of warmer groundwater temperature are still not understood sufficiently. The quality of groundwater is based on (a) the absence of hazardous substances like heavy metals, pollutants, and pathogenic germs, and (b) the physio-chemical properties including pH, salinity, and concentration of dissolved organic carbon as Fe^{2+} and Mn^{2+} (Riedel, 2019). While the quality of drinking water is well protected legally (Directive (EU) 2020/2184, 2020), the ecological consequences (quality) of groundwater warming such as degradation of pollutants, retention of nutrients, or elimination of pathogenic microorganisms has not been studied sufficiently yet (Griebler et al., 2019).

Several impact pathways have been identified consisting of (a) increasing water temperatures, (b) changing groundwater tables, and (c) sea water intrusion in the case of coastal aquifers. For shallow groundwater bodies to a depth of 60 m, it can be said that the temperatures are rising near-linearly to the land surface temperatures (Benz et al., 2017). For the application of PTES systems, similar effects of groundwater warming and ground warming are to be projected. Especially shallow water bodies with higher recharging rates are prone to accelerated groundwater temperature warming, therefore needing special consideration in the PTES planning phase (Kløve et al., 2014).

Similar to the Marstal or Dronninglund PTES, a monitoring system is necessary to follow the changes in ground-temperature and related groundwater temperature (Schmidt and Sørensen, 2018; Sifnaios et al., 2023a). Since groundwater temperatures in northern European cold-water springs are estimated to show temperature increases of +0.7 (RCP2.6 scenario) to +5.9 K (RCP8.5 scenario) by 2086 (Jyvasjarvi et al., 2015), a differentiation of climate change related and PTES related increase is necessary. The warming of shallow aquifers is closely related to the increased average land temperature and has reached + 1 K today, compared to pre-industrial times. By the end of the 21st century, temperatures of +10 K are possible (Neidhardt and Shao, 2023).

One of the most important changes related to increased groundwater temperature is the intensification of microbial metabolic rate. Similarly to microbial activity in the soil, the effects of groundwater warming on microbes are complex and involve a variety of microorganisms and aquifer properties, which vary at small scale (Griebler et al., 2015). In addition to microorganism, groundwater contains a meio- and macrofauna consisting mainly of crustaceans, mites, and snails. These species contribute to the purification of ground water and natural quality management. This fauna is perfectly adapted to the temperature and the chemical

conditions of the groundwater and sensitive to changes (Danielopol et al., 2003). Groundwater biota thrive in high oxygen levels, thus a temperature-related decrease of dissolved oxygen can severely impact these organisms and even render some aquifers inhabitable (Riedel, 2019).

The diversity of aquifer microbial communities can, however, also be increased and the microbial community structure can be changed upon temperature increases (Neidhardt and Shao, 2023). Temperature rise in groundwaters thus has microbiological and biogeochemical impacts on aquatic ecosystems (Bonte et al., 2013a; Hall et al., 2008). It can be stated that especially eutrophic shallow aquifers are vulnerable to rising temperatures, as more degradable organic matter and nutrients are available (Griebler et al., 2016; Neidhardt and Shao, 2023). Additionally, an increase in groundwater temperature of 2-8 °C leads to a decreased capability of water to dissolve gases like oxygen and thus affecting aquatic life (Previati and Crosta, 2021). A temperature increase of 1 °C is connected to a 4 % oxygen concentration reduction and a drop in pH of 0.02 due to increased CO₂ concentration (Riedel, 2019). Moreover, temperature changes observed for an ATEs system in the Netherlands showed a shift in redox conditions of the aquifer due to a temperature increase from 11 °C to 25 °C (Bonte et al., 2013a). Increased temperatures also lead to increased solutions of mineral aggregates in warmer groundwater, which affects aquatic organisms as well. Higher temperatures can also directly accelerate degradation of pollutants in the groundwater. Thermodynamic data suggests that concentration of inorganic pollutants (except for arsenic), however, can decrease with higher temperatures.

These diverging effects resulting from warmer groundwater bodies highlight that no general conclusion can be drawn regarding the effects of specific temperature increases on PTES sites and that individual, site-specific, and seasonal research is necessary. In the past, scientific studies on temperature-associated changes in groundwater quality predominantly focused on geothermal energy use and concluded that changes in the groundwater composition are only relevant for temperatures > 40 °C, except for arsenic, which is already mobilized at moderate temperatures (Bonte et al., 2013b; Griebler et al., 2016). However, *in-situ* studies also showed that even a temperature increase of 7 K leads to observable cation concentration changes (Saito et al., 2016). Warmer groundwater is also associated with a higher Silicon, Potassium and Fluorine concentrations, with F being a contaminant of concern (Riedel, 2019). This further highlights the necessity for individual assessment and the need for further research on groundwater quality changes in lower temperature ranges.

It is worthwhile to state, however, that compared to technologies that use the groundwater body itself (ATEs) or rock formations for storing thermal energy (BTES), the thermal energy input of PTES to their surroundings is intrinsically lower, thus also leading to lower risks of negatively impacting the ecosystem.

4.2.5.5 Groundwater levels and layers

Apart from the warming of groundwater, there is the possible risk of connecting different groundwater levels that used to be spatially delimited. This can lead to tremendous changes in the condition of each groundwater body related to concentration, temperature or filtration rate and can potentially negatively impact the quality

of the groundwater. If the hydrogeology of a specific site indicates that multiple unconnected groundwater bodies are present within the construction depth of the PTES, special precautions and in-depth understanding of the hydrogeology might be necessary to estimate the potential environmental risks connected to the mixing of groundwater bodies. The most important risk factors connected to unexpected damage in the past are a combination of following occurrences: layer-complexes with varying lithographic properties, layered groundwater bodies, karstification, geological fault systems, gas deposits, artesian aquifers, and old mining sites (Lehmphul, 2015). Naturally project sites for PTES should be chosen to best avoid these occurrences.

4.2.5.6 Flora, fauna and habitat

Flora, fauna, and habitats form the foundation of ecosystems, contributing to biodiversity and the overall functioning of the natural environment. Large-scale projects that include construction in undeveloped areas, areas of high conservation value, or occurrence of protected or endangered animal and plant species, therefore require special attention.

Detailed surveys might be necessary for sufficient ecological assessment if losses of land, fragmentation, effects of impairment, or separation effects are to be expected. This also applies if endangered or protected species or habitats are present. Indicator animal families can help to assess effects on biodiversity, sensibility against intrusion, and ecological function for a given project area. For infrastructure projects and mining, Eberhartinger-Tafill (2019) suggests indicators groups according to Table 9. This may also result in seasonal restrictions during construction to avoid negative effects during nesting etc.

TABLE 9: ANIMAL GROUPS AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP AFTER EBERHARTINGER-TAFILL (2019); (x) INDICATING RELEVANCE FOR SOME ASPECTS OR SPECIES FOR THE HABITAT TYPE, X INDICATING RELEVANCE FOR THE HABITAT TYPE

Habitat type/Group	Flowing water	Standing water	Semi-aquatic zones/wet meadows	Terrestrial areas - forests	Open land – meadows, pastures, dry grasslands
Fish	x	x	(x)		
Amphibians		x	(x)		
Dragonflies	x	x	(x)		
Beetles		(x)			x
Butterflies			(x)	X	x
Grasshoppers and mantises			(x)		x
Bats	(x)	(x)	(x)	x	(x)
Birds	x	(x)	(x)	x	x

The potential temperature changes of water bodies can also lead to habitat changes or loss. For example: lowering the groundwater level or changes in flooding behavior can affect the soil quality and aquatic life. Also, the potential of occurrence of non-native problematic species on recultivated land can have significant ecological implications that are specific to the project area. The scope of the survey can be reduced, however, if the project site is of minor importance regarding nature conservation and if the impacts are expected to be very local. Since PTES systems are often built in close proximity to DHNs, it can often be presumed that the planned project is within an area of low ecological value.

4.2.5.7 Climate: Direct carbon emissions

Ecological implications related to climate change can be categorized into direct and indirect emissions. The former arise directly from processes such as combustion of fossil fuels, emission from vehicles, or on-site industrial processes. The latter arise as a consequence of an activity but not at the location of the activity itself like grey energy in materials (Martínez Blanco et al., 2015). Whereas the material choice and implementation have crucial influence on the indirect emissions related to the construction of PTES, this section focuses on the direct emissions that result from charging the system.

While it is important to reduce the emissions during the construction phase, it is necessary to note that the biggest environmental impacts are expected to arise from the energy consumption during the operational phase. A study focusing on the entire life phases of ATES and BTES also came to the conclusion that the biggest contribution of environmental burdens stems from the electricity requirements during operation (Tomasetta, 2025).

The potential temperature changes of water bodies can also lead to habitat changes or loss. For example: lowering the groundwater level or changes in flooding behavior can affect the soil quality and aquatic life. Also, the potential of occurrence of non-native problematic species on recultivated land can have significant ecological implications that are specific to the project area. The scope of the survey can be reduced, however, if the project site is of minor importance regarding nature conservation and if the impacts are expected to be very local. Since PTES systems are often built in close proximity to DHNs, it can often be presumed that the planned project is within an area of low ecological value.

4.2.5.8 Land use and land sealing

Land area can be considered as a distinct environmental asset, particularly regarding land sealing and land consumption. Both the quantity and quality of land and soil may be affected, and it is essential to account for soil functions and their alterations. Special consideration should be given to ecologically sensitive and protected areas or soil types. These include requirements under the *Alpine Soil Conservation Protocol* (2005), including geogenic or anthropogenic areas of importance. To adequately assess the ecological implications, it may be useful to subdivide the study area into subregions based on ecologically functional, physio geographic, or morphological criteria. The land demand required for the establishment of the PTES facility should be precisely quantified. Furthermore, the anticipated impacts of the project on soil functions should be estimated. Wherever possible, soil erosion, compaction, and loss of organic matter should be avoided. In general, a minimal degree of land sealing should be aimed for, and underutilized areas may be synergistically employed through revegetation measures. In this context, the management of excavated soil is crucial. Prior to re-use, it should undergo a thorough quality assessment (in accordance with national landfill ordinance). In areas with high soil water retention, attention should be given to compensating for the loss of the soil's retention capacity. Reclamation measures should be considered to restore affected soil functions (Eberhartinger-Tafill, 2019).

4.2.6 Legal factors

The following section covers legally relevant aspects that have an influence on the environmental implications of PTES projects. The main aspects considered are regulations on groundwater, Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), Biodiversity and lastly light emissions.

4.2.6.1 Regulations on groundwater

While the quality of drinking water is legally well protected within the European Union (Directive (EU) 2020/2184, 2020), the quality of groundwater bodies is not clearly anchored in legal regulations. Effects that have not been studied sufficiently yet include degradation of pollutants, retention of nutrients, or elimination of pathogenic microorganisms and have therefore not resulted in legally binding documents (Griebler et al., 2019). There are national guidelines that are issued by associations such as the VDI ("Verein Deutscher Ingenieure") and DWA ("Deutsche Vereinigung für Wasserwirtschaft, Abwasser und Abfall") in Germany, or the ÖWAV ("Österreichischer Wasser- und Abfallwirtschaftsverband") in Austria, which can support the

planning body. However, these guidelines are often supplemented by regional authorities, which differ in their recommendations or framework conditions (Griebler et al., 2015). For shallow geothermal energy in closed systems, for example, it is estimated that the influence on the groundwater body for small plants (5 or less drillings) is limited to a depth of 10 m. This is also applicable for larger plants as long as the annual thermal energy balance is close to zero. If the annual balance is not assumed, decisions are required on a case-by-case basis (VDI 4640 Blatt 1, 2010). For energy storage applications with storage temperatures that exceed 40 °C, it is merely pointed out that influences on competing groundwater bodies must be ruled out during system planning. Sterilizing effects for temperatures exceeding 60 °C are mentioned but not regarded as critical and are also considered to be reversible as long as no nutrients from drilling fluids are being introduced (VDI 4640 Blatt 3, 2001). The situation is different for PTES systems, where high water temperatures are stored for extended periods of time. Whether the warming of groundwater is within the state-of-the-art recommendations, thus depends on the specific hydrogeological situation and again on the soil's thermal conductivity.

More project-specific legal hard boundary constraints have been formulated by Scholliers et al. (2024), referring to legal allowance to heat groundwater. This is often an issue for BTES or ATES systems. In case the groundwater body is above or at the level of the PTES system, this can be applicable as well. This situation, however, is not only legally more demanding it is also technically challenging and more cost intensive.

4.2.6.2 Environmental impact assessment (EIA)

The EIA procedure ensures that environmental concerns are considered from the beginning of a new project. This subsection is not intended to guide the reader through the process of conducting an EIA, but to extract important environmental aspects for the planning, construction, operation and EoL phases of a PTES system. EIA provides a framework for systematically considering ecological, social, and economic factors associated with planned developments. According to the Directive 2011/92, (2011) and the Directive 2014/52/EU, (2014) of the European Parliament on the assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects, the EIA shall cover the direct and indirect effects of a project on the factors (a) human beings, fauna and flora, (b) soil, water, air climate and the landscape, (c) material assets and the cultural heritage; (d) the interaction between the factors referred to in points (a), (b) and (c).

If the project aligns with certain categories of the EIA Annex I, an EIA will be mandatory, for Annex II a case-by-case decision is necessary, or thresholds or criteria set by the Member State will be applicable. In Annex II paragraph 3 (b), industrial installations for carrying gas, steam and hot water are listed. Paragraph 10 (g) addresses infrastructure projects such as dams and installations designed to hold water or store it on a long-term basis. In this case, the selection criteria set out in Annex III shall be considered, which describes the characteristics and location of the project and the characteristics of the potential impact.

The scope of significant effects should cover direct effects and any indirect, secondary, cumulative, transboundary, short-term, medium-term, long-term, permanent, and temporary as well as positive and

negative effects of the project. It should also consider the environmental protection objectives established at Union or Member State level which are relevant to the project. Additionally, a description of the forecasting methods or evidence used to identify and assess the significant effects on the environment must be provided. This includes details of difficulties (for example technical deficiencies or lack of knowledge) and the main uncertainties involved.

In respect to the location of the project, the absorption capacity of the natural environment needs to be considered in terms of environmental sensitivity. This includes the existing land use, the relative abundance, quality and regenerative capacity of natural resources in the area. The absorption capacity of the natural environment needs to be considered especially focusing on wetlands, coastal zones, mountain and forest areas, nature reserves and parks as well as classified protected areas under Member States' legislation. Environmental impacts of project areas within national parks or areas of protection like Natura 2000 areas (Directive 2014/52/EU, 2014) have to be assessed accordingly. Naturally densely populated areas and landscapes of historical, cultural or archaeological significance must also be considered in terms of their environmental sensitivity.

The characteristics of each impact factor and their interactions must be examined with particular attention to the extent of the impact (including the geographical area and the size of the affected population), the nature and magnitude of the impact, its complexity and likelihood, as well as its duration, frequency, and potential reversibility.

4.2.6.3 Member States' EIA application

Considering the demonstrators that are studied in TREASURE, the Member State's applications for the EIA shall be stated in Table 10.

TABLE 10: NATIONAL EIA IMPLICATION IN THE DEMONSTRATOR'S MEMBER STATES

Member State	EIA application
Austria	<i>(Umweltverträglichkeitsprüfungsgesetz 2000, 1994)</i>
Denmark	<i>(Miljø- og Ligestillingsministeriet, 2021)</i>
France	<i>(Evaluation environnementale (Articles R122-1 à R122-27), 2005)</i>
Germany	<i>(Bundesministerium der Justiz und für Verbraucherschutz, 1990)</i>
Poland	<i>(Ustawę z dnia 3 października 2008 r. o udostępnianiu informacji o środowisku i jego ochronie, udziale społeczeństwa w ochronie środowiska oraz o ocenach oddziaływania na środowisko, 2008)</i>
Serbia	<i>(ЗАКОН о процени утицаја на животну средину, 2024)</i>

4.2.6.4 Biodiversity

It requires national governments to define areas of conservation of flora and fauna species, by setting up a coherent European network. Biodiversity, with particular attention to species and habitats which are protected are consolidated under the Council Directive 92/43/EEC, (1992) and the Directive 2009/147/EC, (2009) formulated as a response to the Berne Convention. These areas are more commonly referred to as Natura 2000 areas. The 2009/147/EC Directive on the conservation of wild birds aims to protect all European wild birds by declaring Special Protection Areas and can also be relevant.

4.2.6.5 Light emission

Light emissions are another environmental consideration, as artificial lighting can alter natural ecosystems, disrupt species behavior, and contribute to broader ecological imbalances. The CIE 150:2017 "Guide on the Limitation of the Effects of Obtrusive Light from Outdoor Lighting Installations" shall therefore be mentioned here. This, however, will most likely only be applicable during the construction phase of the project and even then only during very limited hours of the day (CIE TC 5-28, 2017).

4.3 Results expert consultation

In total, 21 experts and their contacts were invited to participate in the survey. Out of the 21 invitations sent, 16 completed questionnaires were returned, corresponding to a response rate of approximately 76 %.

Out of the 16 experts who participated in the survey, 13 had previously been involved in a feasibility study for a PTES project. Four experts have direct experience with PTES project implementation, while six participants have been working on PTES-related topics for some time but have neither participated in a feasibility study nor in an implemented project. Seven respondents are active in research on PTES, and only one participant reported having no prior experience with PTES projects. Since the question was designed as a multiple-choice item, the total number of responses exceeds the number of participants. The distribution of the reported experience profiles is shown in Figure 20.

FIGURE 20: SURVEY RESULTS REGARDING THE RESPONDENTS’ EXPERIENCE WITH PTES PROJECTS

The summarized assessments of the negative environmental impacts of a PTES project on the respective environmental parameters, submitted by the 16 experts, are presented in Figure 21 using boxplot diagrams. In the boxplot diagrams, the horizontal red line within each box represents the median of the expert ratings, whereas the “x” marker denotes the mean value. The individual points plotted outside the whiskers represent statistical outliers, indicating values that fall substantially beyond the typical response range and thus reflect exceptional or atypical expert judgments.

It is further noteworthy that the maximum rating of five was assigned to only four environmental parameters—water, flora and fauna, landscape, and socio-ecological aspects. In all four cases, the rating of five was provided by a single expert only. This pattern suggests that perceptions of very high negative environmental impacts occurred exclusively in isolated instances and do not reflect the predominant assessment among the surveyed experts.

FIGURE 21: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONSES ON PTES IMPACT ON ENVIRONMENTAL PARAMETERS

The visualization indicates that three environmental parameters are predominantly associated with no or only minor negative environmental impacts. These include air and climate, noise emissions, and light pollution, for which the ratings are mainly concentrated in the lower range of the scale.

A moderate negative environmental impact is attributed to the parameters soil, flora and fauna, waste and deconstruction, and resource use. The ratings for these parameters are primarily located around the mid-range of the scale, suggesting a perceived relevance of potential negative effects without classifying them as severe.

According to the experts, the most pronounced negative environmental impacts are associated with the parameters water, landscape, and socio-ecological aspects. Socio-ecological aspects exhibit a high degree of

variability in expert opinions. The ratings for this parameter are almost evenly distributed between values of one and four, which is reflected in a median value of 2.5.

The open responses addressed social acceptance, traffic-related impacts during the implementation phase, and proximity to historical or archaeological sites as potentially relevant additional aspects.

As described in the methodology section, additional second-level questions were asked for those environmental parameters that were rated three or higher by an expert. The aim of these questions was to determine the specific negative environmental impacts of each parameter more precisely.

The results of these detailed assessments are presented in the following sections. For the environmental parameters air and climate, noise emissions, and light pollution, no further analysis of the detailed responses was conducted. For these parameters, the median rating was one, and only one expert completed the follow-up questions. Due to this limited data basis, further statistical evaluation was considered not meaningful.

The number of responses varies between environmental parameters, as participation in the second level (detailed) questions depended on the individual assessments in the first level of the survey. In addition, some experts discontinued the survey before completing all detailed questions. The respective number of responses (n) is therefore reported for each environmental parameter.

4.3.1 Soil

For the environmental parameter soil, a total of five experts rated the negative impacts of a PTES project with a value of three or higher in the first level of the survey. In accordance with the methodology described above, these experts were subsequently presented with detailed follow-up questions to further specify the perceived negative impacts.

The results of the detailed assessment are shown in Table 11. The evaluated aspects included sealing and compaction, excavation and contamination, and soil quality (including warming, pH value, moisture, and (bio-)chemical properties). For all three aspects, a median value of four was obtained, indicating that the negative impacts were predominantly assessed as high by the responding experts.

TABLE 11: SOIL – RESULTS FROM SECOND-LEVEL ENVIRONMENTAL SURVEY

Impact (1 low - 5 high)	median	mean
sealing & compaction	4	3.6
excavation & contamination	4	3.6
quality (warming, pH, moisture, (bio)chemistry)	4	4.2

In the first survey level, none of the experts awarded the environmental parameter soil the highest rating of five. In contrast, several experts rated individual soil-related aspects with five points in the detailed follow-up questions. This suggests that a general assessment of the soil parameter tends to reflect lower perceived impacts than a more differentiated assessment of specific soil-related factors.

4.3.2 Water

Based on the ratings provided in the first level of the survey, eight experts were initially eligible to complete the detailed follow-up questions for the environmental parameter water. However, one expert did not complete the second level of the questionnaire. Consequently, the detailed assessment of the water-related aspects is based on responses from seven experts.

For the environmental parameter water, detailed follow-up questions were also applied to those experts who rated the impacts in the first level of the survey as moderate to high. In the second level, a differentiated assessment of water-related aspects was conducted, distinguishing between groundwater, surface waters, and water use.

The results of the detailed assessment are presented in Table 12. Within the groundwater-related aspects, groundwater flow and groundwater warming were predominantly rated as having high negative impacts, each with a median value of four. In addition, water use, particularly in terms of potential competition with drinking water supply, received a comparatively higher negative rating, with a median value of three.

TABLE 12: WATER – RESULTS FROM SECOND-LEVEL ENVIRONMENTAL SURVEY

Impact (1 low - 5 high)	Median	Mean
groundwater flow	4	3
groundwater warming	4	4.1
groundwater connectivity (connecting separated groundwater sources)	2	2.1
groundwater pollution	2	1.7
infiltration & stormwater runoff	2	2.1
surface waters	2	2.1
water use (competition with drinking water)	3	3.1

In contrast, the negative impacts on groundwater connectivity, groundwater pollution, infiltration and stormwater runoff, and surface waters were generally assessed as lower, each with a median value of two. It should be noted that for infiltration and stormwater runoff as well as surface waters, at least one expert assigned a high negative impact rating (value of five), indicating a heterogeneous perception of these specific water-related aspects.

4.3.3 Flora and fauna

Based on the ratings for the environmental parameter flora and fauna, seven experts were initially eligible to complete the detailed assessment. One additional expert discontinued the survey during the second level, resulting in detailed responses from five experts for the flora and fauna parameter.

The results of the detailed assessment are shown in Table 13. The evaluated aspects included habitat loss, habitat degradation, habitat fragmentation, and ecologically sensitive and protected areas.

TABLE 13: FLORA AND FAUNA – RESULTS FROM SECOND-LEVEL ENVIRONMENTAL SURVEY

Impact (1 low - 5 high)	Median	Mean
habitat loss	5	4.6
habitat degradation	4	4
habitat fragmentation	4	3.8
ecologically sensitive and protected areas	4	3.6

The aspect habitat loss received the highest rating, with a median value of five. Habitat degradation, habitat fragmentation, and impacts on ecologically sensitive and protected areas were also predominantly rated as high, each with a median value of four.

This result is particularly noteworthy when compared to the assessments from the first survey level. In the first level, the overall median for the environmental parameter *flora and fauna* was 2, while a high variability in expert responses was observed. This indicates that an aggregated overall assessment suggests relatively low negative impacts.

In contrast, the second, more detailed survey level reveals that specific impact pathways can be perceived as having substantially higher negative effects when assessed individually. This discrepancy can be explained by the two-stage survey design: whereas the first level captures an overall evaluation of the environmental parameter, the second level focuses on specific mechanisms of impact that may be perceived as more severe when considered in isolation. Furthermore, it should be noted that the detailed questions were only answered by those experts who had already rated the impact on *flora and fauna* as three or higher in the first survey level.

4.3.4 Landscape

For the environmental parameter landscape, a total of eleven experts were eligible to complete the detailed follow-up questions, of whom two discontinued the survey, resulting in detailed responses from nine experts.

The results of the detailed assessment are shown in Table 14. The evaluated aspects included land use and visual change. The impacts on landscape were already among the highest rated in the first survey level. In the

second level, experts confirmed that the effects on land use and visual change are perceived as significant, with land use being rated slightly higher than visual change.

TABLE 14: LANDSCAPE – RESULTS FROM SECOND-LEVEL ENVIRONMENTAL SURVEY

Impact (1 low - 5 high)	Median	Mean
land use	5	4.3
visual change	4	3.8

The results of the detailed assessment are shown in Table 14. The evaluated aspects included land use and visual change. The impacts on landscape were already among the highest rated in the first survey level. In the second level, experts confirmed that the effects on land use and visual change are perceived as significant, with land use being rated slightly higher than visual change.

4.3.5 Resource use

For the environmental parameter resource use, a total of seven experts were eligible to complete the detailed follow-up questions. Two experts did not complete the follow-up, so the detailed assessment is based on responses from five experts.

The evaluated aspects included material use, environmental burdens of the materials used, and recyclability of materials. The results of the expert assessments are presented in Table 15.

TABLE 15: RESOURCE USE – RESULTS FROM SECOND-LEVEL ENVIRONMENTAL SURVEY

Impact (1 low - 5 high)	Median	Mean
material use	4	3.6
environmental burdens of materials used	4	3.4
recyclability of materials	3	3.2

Material use and environmental burdens of the materials used were predominantly rated as high, each with a median value of four. Recyclability of materials was rated lower, with a median value of three.

In the first level of the survey, none of the experts rated the impact of resource use with the maximum score of five. In the second, more detailed level of the survey, which differentiated the environmental aspect further, the highest rating was given by only one expert. Overall, the results remained within the same range as in the first level. This is consistent with the survey design, as only experts who had previously rated the impact as three or higher in the first level were invited to respond to detailed questions.

4.3.6 Waste and deconstruction

For the environmental parameter waste and deconstruction, a total of four experts were eligible to complete the detailed follow-up questions. One expert did not complete the follow-up, resulting in detailed assessments from three experts.

The results of the detailed assessment are presented in Table 16. The evaluated aspects included dismantling, recycling, and disposal of potentially contaminated materials.

TABLE 16: WASTE AND DECONSTRUCTION – RESULTS FROM SECOND-LEVEL ENVIRONMENTAL SURVEY

Impact (1 low - 5 high)	Median	Mean
dismantling	3	3.3
recycling	3	3.3
potentially contaminated materials & disposal	1	2

The second-level questions were answered by only three experts, producing results similar to those from the first level. While impacts on dismantling and recycling are generally acknowledged, the overall assessment is low, with a median score of three, reflecting both the moderate perceived impact and the small number of respondents. The impact of potentially contaminated materials and their disposal was rated as high by only one expert, resulting in a median score of one.

4.3.7 Socio-ecological aspects

For the environmental parameter socio-ecological aspects, the assessments in the first level of the survey exhibited the largest variability among all environmental parameters. Of the 16 surveyed experts, eight rated the negative impacts as moderate to high. These experts were subsequently asked to differentiate the impacts on specific land use conflicts, particularly concerning agriculture and recreational areas.

For those experts who rated the socio-ecological aspects with a score of three or higher in the first level of the survey, the impacts of land use conflicts related to agriculture and recreational areas were further assessed. The results are presented in Table 17.

TABLE 17: SOCIO-ECOLOGICAL ASPECTS – RESULTS FROM SECOND-LEVEL ENVIRONMENTAL SURVEY

Impact (1 low - 5 high)	Median	Mean
land use conflict (agriculture)	4.5	4.5
land use conflict (recreational areas)	3	3.7

PTES projects were perceived to have a predominantly high impact on conflicts with agricultural land, with experts identifying significant potential negative effects. In contrast, the impact of PTES projects on conflicts

with recreational areas was assessed as lower: four experts rated it as moderate, while only two rated it as high.

4.3.8 Open ended responses

At the end of the second level of the survey, experts were again invited to answer open-ended questions. The aim was to identify missing or additional environmental aspects and to collect general feedback on the survey. Open-ended responses are used to contextualize and complement the quantitative results and are not intended to represent a comprehensive or statistically representative assessment.

Among the additional or further aspects mentioned were:

- The magnitude of negative environmental impacts is strongly dependent on the size and location of the individual PTES project.
- Stormwater management, particularly in the case of site sealing in non-anthropogenically influenced areas.
- Land use conflicts arise on land designated for residential or commercial development, as PTES installations require land, often in urban areas where land use conflicts are common and energy infrastructure is often not a priority. This can lead to strong resistance from the local population.
- The risk of dam failure as a specific hazard associated with PTES projects.

In addition, several experts pointed out methodological aspects of the survey:

- The distinction between the construction and operation phases was considered relevant, as environmental impacts may differ significantly between project phases.
- It was also noted that the survey focused exclusively on negative impacts, without relating them to the potential positive effects of PTES projects. This limitation should be considered when interpreting the results.

The results of the survey are discussed related to the findings from the literature review in the discussion chapter.

5. Discussion

This section discusses the implications derived from the methodology of LCA, PESTEL analysis, and expert consultation. The order of methods is chosen to progressively cover all aspects that PTES can have on the environment.

5.1 Lessons learned for conducting LCAs for PTES

By following a holistic approach via the PESTEL method, the goal of this deliverable is to derive all relevant ecological implications related to the life cycle of a PTES. As a result, this deliverable should provide guidance for conducting LCAs for PTES and describe challenges that can be foreseen. The methodological framework of the ISO 21930 has been identified as a useful tool to provide reproducible results for conducting LCAs with potentially very different components and charging mechanisms. The general approach follows a product system that is described by a construction, an operational, and an EoL phase.

Construction activities result in environmental pollution due to land clearing, machinery-related emissions, demolition combustion, potential use of hazardous chemicals, and the construction materials used (Labaran et al., 2022). During the construction phase of LCA, the precise reflection of the production and installation of the innovative constructive parts for the lid need detailed process understanding. This is also the case for the high-temperature resistant polymer used for the liner material. LCA conducted on the construction phase of LCA have been reported by Solites (Mangold et al., 2011). They focused on gravel-water-filled PTES systems and showed that the foamed glass components and the gravel used for the PTES have the biggest impact on the impact category climate change. They also argued that compared to other technologies that provide thermal energy, the maintenance and the electricity demand for hydraulic pumps during operation can be neglected, while also not considering the EoL phase. More recent studies on the constructional phase of STES showed that PTES have the lowest environmental impact in the categories global warming ($\text{g CO}_2/\text{kWh}_{\text{th}}$), non-renewable energy ($\text{kJ}/\text{kWh}_{\text{th}}$) and mineral extraction ($\text{kJ}/\text{kWh}_{\text{th}}$) compared to water-gravel based systems and TTES (Weise et al., 2026).

While the above-mentioned aspects relate to challenges concerning the system boundary, additional challenges are expected to arise due to the allocation of environmental burdens to the product thermal energy. As DHNs often utilize generation units that provide power and heat (CHPs e.g.), a fair allocation to these two products needs to be derived. There is a multitude of ways to calculate these calculation factors, exergy-based, energy-based, and primary-fuel-input based, which can be found in (Buchenau et al., 2023). In former LCAs on TES, this issue is often simplified by comparing a TES with a conventional gas plant fired by natural gas (Kovács et al., 2025), or by implementing the method of system expansion with substitution as done by (Famiglietti et al., 2021). While these are valid considerations for small-scale systems, this approach must be adapted for assessing the environmental impacts of LTES. This is also necessary because LTES in a DHN potentially replace large amounts of energy compared to a DHN without LTES. Especially the replacement of CO_2 -intensive technologies is one of the biggest ecological benefits of PTES and thus the

methodological approach in assessing the emissions of the replaced units needs to be modeled accurately. Thus, the higher the amount of energy that is transmitted through a PTES throughout its lifetime, the lower the environmental impacts that are connected to the construction phase. This effect is even more prominent when the PTES displaces CO₂-intensive thermal energy. Conversely, the proportion of impacts that result from the construction phase is higher, when a PTES is entirely charged with renewable energy in an already largely decarbonized DHN. Because of this relationship, extra care must be taken with the LCI of the energy generation units. Inaccuracies in the modeling of these steps can result in major discrepancies as the cumulative energy throughout the lifetime reaches tremendous amounts (around 2 TWh for an 80 GWh storage for 25 years with a cycle number of 1). This has also been derived for other TES systems. Previous works on BTES and ATES found that the electricity required for operation throughout the 25 year long life cycle has the biggest environmental impact (Tomasetta, 2013).

The EoL phase and considered recyclability or repurposing scenarios have to be developed on a case-by-case basis.

The complexity of the land use also needs to be considered thoroughly, especially since the construction of PTES requires substantial areas. LANCA provides a well-established tool to assess the changes in land quality for transformative and occupational land usage, resulting in a single point on land use impact, the soil quality index (Beck et al., 2010). This also becomes evident when looking at the graphical representation of the derived ecological implications from the PESTEL analysis (Figure 22), as soil quality changes are a central aspect of the environmental dimension. Also, ecosystem services related to groundwater are considered in LANCA which is another central aspect of the environmental implications.

System boundaries need to be carefully considered too, and the functional unit shall be chosen so that different PTES are comparable. The authors suggest 1 MWh of thermal energy provided to the already existing DHN. The ability to compare the results of an LCA study on PTES with those of another LTES-LCA study, as well as with results from DHNs without LTES, is essential for making informed decisions regarding both currently planned (Table 5) and potential future PTES cases. This also serves as a basis to proactively plan PTES projects and to minimize the environmental burdens connected to the PTES life cycle.

5.2 Indicators for environmental assessment from PESTEL analysis

The following section should discuss the compilation of the most important ecological implications that were derived from the PESTEL analysis based on literature research. The interconnected nature of the single dimensions and the focus areas can be seen in Figure 22. The majority of impact arrows flow into parameters defined for the environmental dimension. Especially the parameters groundwater, soil, and climate can be considered as areas of special focus and thus as areas that require increased attention.

FIGURE 22: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF ECOLOGICAL IMPLICATION CATEGORIES AFTER PESTEL ANALYSIS AND THEIR INTERCONNECTED NATURE

Political

The political dimension within the PESTEL framework highlights that LTES (including PTES) are imperative for decarbonizing the DHNs of the future. The political dimension has been shown to have ecological implications, namely in the form of reduced GHG emissions resulting from the utilization of these technologies. Quantitative analysis of this phenomenon has been conducted for Denmark and its neighboring countries by

Sifnaios et al. (2023c). Their findings indicate that the incorporation of LTES into the DHNs results in a more rapid decarbonization process compared to scenarios that do not include LTES.

Economic

The material selection, constrained by cost-effectiveness imperatives, gives rise to material-specific ecological ramifications, particularly during the construction phase of a PTES. Moreover, ensuring the economic feasibility of the project is essential for its implementation, which in turn enables positive environmental impacts due to the decarbonized nature of the district heating network (DHN).

Social

The key ecological implications within the social dimension can be broadly categorized into three areas: (1) public health considerations, (2) social acceptance, and (3) interactions with culturally significant sites. Among these, the latter is generally regarded as secondary, given the overriding technical requirements associated with PTES projects.

Technology

A major ecological implication that can be derived from the technological pillar is to avoid the construction of PTES in groundwater saturated zones. This technical prerequisite also reduces adverse environmental effects. In general, the selection of a project site must be undertaken with the highest degree of diligence in order to minimize potential environmental risks. A second implication is based on the material choice, respectively the lifetime and thus the burdens connected to replacing material during the lifetime of a PTES. It shall be noted here, however, that LCAs that are conducted for systems consuming energy throughout a relatively long lifetime (as is the case for PTES), show that the burdens connected to the material production are often very small (Hischier et al., 2020; Khasreen et al., 2009). For example, even for prefabricated industrial buildings with a considered lifetime of 50 years, the use phase accounts for approximately 76 % of the emissions (Bonamente and Cotana, 2015). Thus, impacts that lead to permanent changes to the ecosystem (groundwater warming, soil warming) and energy consumption throughout the use phase have to be considered with great care for detail compared to one-time incisions of the environment.

Environmental

Although there is broad consensus within the scientific community regarding the necessity of monitoring and safeguarding soil and groundwater quality, numerous impact pathways remain insufficiently investigated. Consequently, case-specific assessments of soil and groundwater conditions, potential quality changes, and appropriate risk mitigation measures are indispensable and should be systematically complemented by continuous monitoring. The divergent effects of rising soil and groundwater temperatures on their respective ecosystem services, combined with the highly site-specific nature of these processes, preclude the formulation of general recommendations beyond the overarching principle of minimizing ecological disturbance. In the broader context of climate change, however, it is essential to evaluate PTES within the integrated framework of DHNs. Such systems offer substantial potential for decarbonizing the heating sector and thus contribute positively to the environment by replacing technologies with significantly higher GHG

emissions. While construction inevitably entails temporary emissions, these must be weighed against the long-term environmental benefits, with assessments carefully contextualized to capture the full balance of impacts.

Legal

While the legal framework governing the protection of drinking water is clearly defined, comparable regulations addressing groundwater warming and its implications for water quality remain underdeveloped. Existing guidelines issued by professional associations may provide valuable orientation for planning authorities; however, they lack binding legal force. In light of the EIA and the Biodiversity Directive, it becomes evident that project sites must be approached with great consideration, particularly with respect to areas of special ecological significance or areas requiring strict protection. By contrast, legal considerations related to light and noise emissions are of secondary importance, as such impacts are minimal during PTES operation and largely confined to the construction phase.

5.3 Implications derived from Expert Consultations

This chapter interprets the results of the expert survey in relation to the findings of the literature review. All environmental parameters are briefly revisited and discussed to assess the consistency between expert judgement and existing research.

5.3.1 Soil

Overall, the environmental parameter soil was assessed as relevant (median = 2), with the median value located slightly below the midpoint of the one to five scale. In the detailed assessment, the environmental factors sealing & compaction as well as excavation and contamination were rated with a median of four, indicating a comparatively higher negative impact. Both aspects are also widely discussed in the literature and are generally considered manageable through appropriate technical and planning measures.

One factor that was neither explicitly addressed in the survey nor mentioned in the open-ended questions, but is frequently highlighted in the literature, is soil warming. Soil temperature changes can affect several other environmental parameters, such as groundwater as well as flora and fauna, and should therefore be considered when implementing PTES projects. It is also useful to relate soil warming to depth, because seasonal temperature fluctuations mainly affect near-surface layers, while deeper soil shows less natural variation and can therefore be more influenced by PTES-induced warming.

5.3.2 Water

The environmental parameter water was generally rated with a median of 2.5, with the median value located close to the midpoint of the one to five scale. In the detailed assessment, impacts on groundwater quality, groundwater flow, and groundwater warming were rated as high (median = 4). In contrast, impacts on groundwater connectivity (connecting separated groundwater sources), groundwater pollution, infiltration & stormwater runoff, surface waters (median = 2), and water use (competition with drinking water) (median = 3) were assessed as less relevant.

Notably, the impacts that were rated as high by the experts are also addressed in the current literature, which identifies groundwater-related effects as key environmental considerations for PTES projects.

5.3.3 Flora and Fauna

The assessments of flora and fauna show a differentiated picture with relatively high variability. Although the overall result of the first assessment level for this environmental parameter shows a median of two, the more detailed evaluation rated individual aspects, particularly habitat loss, habitat degradation, and habitat fragmentation, as partially high in terms of negative impact.

These results are noteworthy as they indicate a discrepancy between aggregated overall assessments and the evaluation of specific impact pathways. The high variability suggests that the relevance of impacts on

flora and fauna strongly depends on local site conditions. These findings are consistent with the Austrian guideline for environmental impact assessments, which emphasizes that ecological impacts become particularly relevant when PTES projects are implemented in near-natural or ecologically sensitive areas (Eberhartinger-Tafill, 2019).

At the same time, the literature also points out that PTES facilities are often located near existing district heating networks and therefore in already anthropogenically influenced areas with generally lower ecological value. This may explain why most experts expect only low to moderate impacts, while some anticipate significantly higher risks under specific scenarios.

5.3.4 Landscape

The environmental parameter landscape was rated by the experts with a median value of three, representing the highest overall impact among all assessed environmental parameters, particularly regarding land use and visual changes. The median value of five for land use indicates that land take is perceived as the central landscape-related impact, while visual impacts, with a median value of four, are attributed a slightly lower but still high level of influence.

These results are consistent with the literature, which identifies land consumption and landscape alteration as key environmental impacts of large-scale energy infrastructure. Although PTES facilities are technically relatively simple, they require substantial land areas. The expert assessment emphasizes that the landscape impacts are also strongly influenced by the space requirements and visibility of the facilities, and not solely by emissions.

5.3.5 Resource use

The results for resource use indicate that material consumption and the associated environmental burdens are perceived as particularly relevant, while the recyclability of the materials used is rated slightly lower. Despite the limited number of responses in the second assessment level, a consistent picture of a moderate negative impact emerges.

The literature notes that short service lives of linings or insulation materials can lead to more frequent interventions and, consequently, higher resource use. The comparatively low relevance attributed to recyclability in the assessment should not only be interpreted as a prioritisation of functional or technical requirements. Rather, it reflects the understanding that many PTES components, depending on the specific system design, are generally recyclable, and that the overall environmental and resource implications of end of life treatment are therefore considered limited.

5.3.6 Waste and deconstruction

The environmental parameter waste and deconstruction was generally assessed as having low relevance. Both dismantling and recycling were rated as having low negative impacts. The disposal of potentially

contaminated materials was predominantly considered to pose a very low risk, with only a single deviating expert opinion. A likely explanation for this assessment is that PTES systems typically do not contain contaminated materials, which substantially limits the environmental risks associated with their disposal.

These results align with common planning practices for PTES projects that aim for a long material lifespan. Occasionally higher scores can therefore be interpreted as reflecting specific local conditions rather than general relevance.

5.3.7 Socio-ecological aspects

The environmental parameter “Socio-ecological aspects” showed the widest range of responses in the first evaluation phase.

Land-use conflicts are an important aspect that should be considered when planning future PTES projects. This is particularly true for agricultural land, where experts rated land-use conflicts as having a particularly significant socio-ecological impact.

These findings are supported by the literature, which highlights land-use competition as a key factor for the social acceptance of energy infrastructure (Baur et al., 2022; “Directive 2014/52/EU,” 2014).

5.3.8 Air quality and climate, noise emission and light pollution

The impacts on air quality and climate, noise emissions, and light pollution were consistently rated as minor by the experts. This generally aligns with the specialist literature, which rarely addresses these impacts and, if at all, primarily associates them with the construction phase. They are considered easily manageable through regulation and mitigation measures.

6. Conclusion

The assessment of PTES systems through LCA (Life Cycle Assessment), PESTEL analysis (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental and Legal), and expert consultation highlights the complex and multi-dimensional environmental implications associated with their life cycle. The construction, operation, and end-of-life phases each contribute differently to overall environmental impacts. Construction activities, particularly the production and installation of innovative structural components and the use of materials, need to be modeled with in-depth process understanding. Operational impacts are closely linked to energy throughput, with the displacement of CO₂-intensive technologies providing one of the greatest ecological benefits of PTES. This underscores the importance of carefully modeling energy generation units and allocation methods to ensure accurate assessment of avoided emissions, particularly in large-scale long-term PTES integrated into district heating networks (DHNs).

Land use and ecosystem services, notably soil quality and groundwater, emerge as critical considerations. Tools such as LANCA can systematically quantify impacts on soil and groundwater, supporting comparability across different PTES systems. PESTEL analysis further demonstrates that environmental outcomes are interlinked with political, economic, social, technological, and legal dimensions. While political support and regulatory frameworks can accelerate decarbonization, site-specific planning and material choices influence both construction impacts and long-term operational performance. Continuous monitoring and case-specific assessment are essential to manage uncertainties, particularly for soil and groundwater temperature changes, which may have highly site-specific ecological consequences.

The environmental performance of PTES systems is strongly influenced by the CO₂ intensity of the operational energy flows as well as by informed decisions regarding construction methods, material selection, and site characteristics. A systematic LCA, complemented by a PESTEL analysis and expert evaluations, provides a robust framework for identifying relevant environmental impacts, supporting evidence-based design choices, and enhancing the overall sustainability of PTES. A precise assessment of both construction-related impacts and long-term operational effects is essential to ensure that PTES ultimately delivers a net environmental benefit. This analytical foundation underpins the LCAs that will be conducted for the TREASURE demonstration projects within the scope of Deliverable 6.2. A rigorous evaluation approach enables the early identification of potential risks during the planning phase and supports the optimization of the environmental advantages associated with PTES.

The results of the expert survey indicate that none of the investigated environmental parameters are considered fundamentally critical for PTES. However, negative impacts are strongly dependent on on-site conditions, system design, and project-specific characteristics. It should be noted that the expert survey explicitly focused on negative impacts and did not compare PTES to alternative technologies. The literature supports this assessment by emphasizing the importance of project-specific environmental assessments, careful site selection, and accompanying monitoring measures. From the experts' perspective, PTES is

therefore perceived less as an environmental problem but more as a technically controllable infrastructure with manageable environmental impacts.

PTES may offer substantial environmental benefits compared to other thermal energy storage or generation technologies with significantly higher environmental footprints. In this context, the choice of heat source used to charge the PTES system during operation plays a particularly important role in determining its overall environmental performance.

Overall, PTES has strong potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions in heat supply, especially when it replaces carbon intensive thermal sources (such as fossil sources). However, achieving these benefits requires careful attention to construction related impacts, how emissions are allocated, and land use considerations. Consistent monitoring, comprehensive LCAs, and sensitivity to site specific ecological conditions are essential to ensure that PTES is deployed sustainably within sustainable heating systems.

7. References

- Ammerer, G., 2024. „Sonnenspeicher Süd“ Geotechnical, Legal, and Socio-Ecological Challenges in the Repurposing of the Weitendorf Basalt Quarry.
- Andersson, O., 2007. BO 01 ATEs system for heating and cooling in Malmö, in: Paksoy, H.Ö. (Ed.), Thermal Energy Storage for Sustainable Energy Consumption, NATO Science Series. Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht, pp. 235–238. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-5290-3_14
- Andreasi Bassi, S., Biganzoli, F., Ferrara, N., Amadei, A., Valente, A., Sala, S., Ardenne, F., 2023. Updated characterisation and normalisation factors for the environmental footprint 3.1 method. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/798894>
- Balaji, I., 2025. What it takes to be the world’s greenest hotel. URL <https://www.thehindubusinessline.com/news/what-it-takes-to-be-the-worlds-greenest-hotel/article8728903.ece>
- Bare, J., 2011. TRACI 2.0: the tool for the reduction and assessment of chemical and other environmental impacts 2.0. *Clean Technol. Environ. Policy* 13, 687–696. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10098-010-0338-9>
- Baur, D., Emmerich, P., Baumann, M.J., Weil, M., 2022. Assessing the social acceptance of key technologies for the German energy transition. *Energy Sustain. Soc.* 12, 4. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13705-021-00329-x>
- Beck, T., Bos, U., Wittstock, B., Baitz, M., Fischer, M., Sedlbauer, K., 2010. LANCA® - Land Use Indicator Value Calculation in Life Cycle Assessment. <https://doi.org/10.24406/publica-fhg-295004>
- Benz, S.A., Bayer, P., Blum, P., 2017. Global patterns of shallow groundwater temperatures. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 12, 034005. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aa5fb0>
- Bevk, T., Golobič, M., 2020. Contentious eye-catchers: Perceptions of landscapes changed by solar power plants in Slovenia. *Renew. Energy* 152, 999–1010. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2020.01.108>
- Billings, S.A., Ballantyne IV, F., 2013. How interactions between microbial resource demands, soil organic matter stoichiometry, and substrate reactivity determine the direction and magnitude of soil respiratory responses to warming. *Glob. Change Biol.* 19, 90–102. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12029>
- Bloemendal, J.M., Beernik, S., 2020. ransitie open bodemenergiesysteem Koppert-Cress naar verhoogde opslagtemperatuur.
- Bonamente, E., Cotana, F., 2015. Carbon and Energy Footprints of Prefabricated Industrial Buildings: A Systematic Life Cycle Assessment Analysis. *Energies* 8, 12685–12701. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en8112333>
- Bonte, M., Röling, W.F.M., Zaura, E., van der Wielen, P.W.J.J., Stuyfzand, P.J., van Breukelen, B.M., 2013a. Impacts of shallow geothermal energy production on redox processes and microbial communities. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 47, 14476–14484. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es4030244>
- Bonte, M., van Breukelen, B.M., Stuyfzand, P.J., 2013b. Temperature-induced impacts on groundwater quality and arsenic mobility in anoxic aquifer sediments used for both drinking water and shallow geothermal energy production. *Water Res.* 47, 5088–5100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2013.05.049>
- Bott, C., Dressel, I., Bayer, P., 2019. State-of-technology review of water-based closed seasonal thermal energy storage systems. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 113, 109241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.06.048>
- Bridger, D.W., Allen, D.M., 2010. Heat transport simulations in a heterogeneous aquifer used for aquifer thermal energy storage (ATES). *Can. Geotech. J.* 47, 96–115. <https://doi.org/10.1139/T09-078>

- Brunner, C., Fink, C., Knotzer, A., Leusbrock, I., Selvička, E., Spörk-Dür, M., van Helden, W., 2024. Infrastrukturen der Zukunft: Wärmespeicher. AEE - Inst. Für Nachhalt. Technol., nachhaltige technologien. https://www.aee-intec.at/zeitung/nachhaltige_technologien-4-2024/10/
- Brunstroem, C., Larsson, M., Pilebro, H., 1986. Lyckebo project - Thermal Energy Storage in a Rock Cavern. <https://www.osti.gov/etdeweb/biblio/7767762>
- Buchenau, N., Hannen, C., Holzapfel, P., Finkbeiner, M., Hesselbach, J., 2023. Allocation of carbon dioxide emissions to the by-products of combined heat and power plants: A methodological guidance. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Transit.* 4, 100069. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rset.2023.100069>
- Bundesgesetz über die Prüfung der Umweltverträglichkeit (Umweltverträglichkeitsprüfungsgesetz 2000 – UVP-G 2000), 1994.
- Bundesministerium der Justiz und für Verbraucherschutz, 1990. Gesetz über die Umweltverträglichkeitsprüfung (UVPG), BGBl. I 2021, S. 540. <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/uvpg/BJNR102050990.html>
- Chang, I., Lee, M., Cho, G.-C., 2019. Global CO₂ Emission-Related Geotechnical Engineering Hazards and the Mission for Sustainable Geotechnical Engineering. *Energies* 12, 2567. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12132567>
- CIE TC 5-28, 2017. CIE 150:2017 Guide on the Limitation of the Effects of Obtrusive Light from Outdoor Lighting Installations, 2nd Edition. <https://doi.org/10.25039/TR.150.2017>
- Commission Recommendation of 14 March 2023 on Energy Storage – Underpinning a decarbonised and secure EU energy system 2023/C 103/01, 2023.
- Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora, 1992.
- Dahash, A., Michele Bianchi Janetti, M., Ochs, F., 2019a. Numerical Analysis and Evaluation of Large-Scale Hot Water Tanks and Pits in District Heating Systems, in: *Building Simulation*. Presented at the Building Simulation 2019, IBPSA, pp. 1692–1699. <https://doi.org/10.26868/25222708.2019.210566>
- Dahash, A., Ochs, F., Janetti, M.B., Streicher, W., 2019b. Advances in seasonal thermal energy storage for solar district heating applications: A critical review on large-scale hot-water tank and pit thermal energy storage systems. *Appl. Energy* 239, 296–315. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.01.189>
- Danielopol, D.L., Griebler, C., Gunatilaka, A., Notenboom, J., 2003. Present state and future prospects for groundwater ecosystems. *Environ. Conserv.* 30, 104–130. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0376892903000109>
- Directive 2009/147/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 November 2009 on the conservation of wild birds (Codified version), 2009.
- Directive 2011/92/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2011 on the assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment (codification) Text with EEA relevance, 2011.
- Directive 2014/52/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 amending Directive 2011/92/EU on the assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment Text with EEA relevance, 2014.
- Directive (EU) 2020/2184 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2020 on the quality of water intended for human consumption (recast) (Text with EEA relevance), 2020.
- Directive (EU) 2023/2413 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 October 2023 amending Directive (EU) 2018/2001, Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 and Directive 98/70/EC as regards the promotion of energy from renewable sources, and repealing Council Directive (EU) 2015/652, 2023.

- Dominković, D.F., Ćosić, B., Bačelić Medić, Z., Duić, N., 2015. A hybrid optimization model of biomass trigeneration system combined with pit thermal energy storage. *Energy Convers. Manag., Special Issue on Sustainable development of energy, water and environment systems* 104, 90–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2015.03.056>
- DTU International Energy Report 2015: Energy systems integration for the transition to non-fossil energy systems, 2015. Technical University of Denmark. https://backend.orbit.dtu.dk/ws/portalfiles/portal/119583507/DTU_International_Energy_Report_2015_rev.pdf
- Dubey, P., 2021. Efficient Pit project: together with its partners, Solmax is developing the next generation of pit thermal energy storage. *Inf. Infrastruct.* URL https://informedinfrastructure.com/67506/efficient-pit-project-together-with-its-partners-solmax-is-developing-the-next-generation-of-pit-thermal-energy-storage/?utm_source=chatgpt.com (accessed 9.1.25).
- Eberhartinger-Tafill, S., 2019. UVE - Leitfaden. Bundesministerium für Nachhaltigkeit und Tourismus.
- Eggen, G., Vangsnæs, G., 2005. Heat pump for district cooling and heating at Oslo Airport Gardermoen. https://www.sintef.no/globalassets/project/annex29/installasjoner/gshp_gardermoenhp_no1.pdf
- Enserink, M., Van Etteger, R., Van Den Brink, A., Stremke, S., 2022. To support or oppose renewable energy projects? A systematic literature review on the factors influencing landscape design and social acceptance. *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 91, 102740. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102740>
- European Commission, 2019. The European Green Deal. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52019DC0640>
- Evaluation environnementale (Articles R122-1 à R122-27), 2005. https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/codes/section_lc/LEGITEXT000006074220/LEGISCTA000006159331/#LEGISCTA000006159331
- Famiglietti, J., Gerevini, L., Spirito, G., Pozzi, M., Dénarié, A., Scoccia, R., Motta, M., 2021. Environmental Life Cycle Assessment scenarios for a district heating network. An Italian case study. *Energy Rep.* 7, 368–379. <https://doi.org/ISBN:%25202352-4847>
- Fang, J., Wei, S., Shi, G., Cheng, Y., Zhang, X., Zhang, F., Lu, Z., Zhao, X., 2021. Potential effects of temperature levels on soil bacterial community structure. *E3S Web Conf.* 292, 01008. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202129201008>
- Finkbeiner, M., Inaba, A., Tan, R., Christiansen, K., Klüppel, H.-J., 2006. The new international standards for life cycle assessment: ISO 14040 and ISO 14044. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 11, 80–85. <https://doi.org/ISBN:%25200948-3349>
- Fleuchaus, P., Godschalk, B., Stober, I., Blum, P., 2018. Worldwide application of aquifer thermal energy storage – A review. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 94, 861–876. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.06.057>
- Gombert, P., Gueye, A., Haïkel, B.H., Beji, H., Laouafa, F., 2019. Installation of a Thermal Energy Storage Site in an Abandoned Mine in Picardy (France). Part 1: Selection Criteria and Equipment of the Experimental Site.
- Griebler, C., Avramov, M., Hose, G., 2019. Groundwater ecosystems and their services: current status and potential risks, in: Schröter, M., Bonn, A., Klotz, S., Seppelt, R., Baessler, C. (Eds.), *Atlas of Ecosystem Services*. Springer, Cham, Switzerland, pp. 197–203. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-96229-0_31
- Griebler, C., Brielmann, H., Haberer, C.M., Kaschuba, S., Kellermann, C., Stumpp, C., Hegler, F., Kuntz, D., Walker-Hertkorn, S., Lueders, T., 2016. Potential impacts of geothermal energy use and storage of heat on groundwater quality, biodiversity, and ecosystem processes. *Environ. Earth Sci.* 75. <https://publikationen.uni-tuebingen.de/xmlui/handle/10900/84603>

- Griebler, C., Kellermann, C., Stumpp, C., Hegler, F., Kuntz, D., Walker-Hertkorn, S., 2015. Auswirkungen thermischer Veränderungen infolge der Nutzung oberflächennaher Geothermie auf die Beschaffenheit des Grundwassers und seiner Lebensgemeinschaften – Empfehlungen für eine umweltverträgliche Nutzung.
- Gunasekara, S.N., Martin, V., Edén, T., 2021. Distributed Cold Storage in District Cooling.
- Hahne, E., 2000. The ITW solar heating system: an oldtimer fully in action. *Sol. Energy, Large Scale Solar Heating* 69, 469–493. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-092X\(00\)00115-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-092X(00)00115-8)
- Hall, E.K., Neuhauser, C., Cotner, J.B., 2008. Toward a mechanistic understanding of how natural bacterial communities respond to changes in temperature in aquatic ecosystems. *ISME J.* 2, 471–481. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ismej.2008.9>
- Hauschild, M.Z., Rosenbaum, R.K., Stig Irving, O., 2018. Life Cycle Assessment—Theory and Practice.
- Heller, A., 1997. Floating Lid Constructions for Pit Water Storage: A Survey. https://backend.orbit.dtu.dk/ws/portalfiles/portal/218492008/ibe_r011.pdf
- Hellström, G., 2012. UTEs Experiences from Sweden, in: *Proceedings of the REHAU Seminar on Underground Thermal Energy Storage*. London, UK.
- Herbert, D.A., Rastetter, E.B., Shaver, G.R., Ågren, G.I., 1999. Effects of Plant Growth Characteristics on Biogeochemistry and Community Composition in a Changing Climate. *Ecosystems* 2, 367–382. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s100219900086>
- Hesaraki, A., Holmberg, S., Haghighat, F., 2015. Seasonal thermal energy storage with heat pumps and low temperatures in building projects—A comparative review. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 43, 1199–1213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.12.002>
- Hischier, R., Reale, F., Castellani, V., Sala, S., 2020. Environmental impacts of household appliances in Europe and scenarios for their impact reduction. *J. Clean. Prod.* 267, 121952. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121952>
- Ho, J.K.-K., 2014. Formulation of a Systemic PEST Analysis for Strategic Analysis.
- Hoes, H., Desmedt, J., Robeyn, N., van Bael, J., 2006. Experiences with ATES applications in Belgium: Operational results and energy saving, in: *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Thermal Energy Storage*.
- Horn, R., Maier, S., Hong, S.H., 2021. LANCA-Introduction and Status. https://www.lifecyclecenter.se/wp-content/uploads/2.-LANCA_Rafael-Horn.pdf
- Huijbregts, M., Steinmann, Z.J.N., Elshout, P.M., Stam, G., Verones, F., Vieira, M.D.M., Hollander, A., Zijp, M., van Zelm, R., 2016. ReCiPe 2016 : A harmonized life cycle impact assessment method at midpoint and endpoint level Report I: Characterization (No. 0104), RIVM Report - 2016. National Institute for Public Health and the Environment - Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport. <https://rivm.openrepository.com/entities/publication/3d19272d-3ee1-4d95-bbc7-3ad21f0a769e>
- IEA, 1998. *Heat Pumping Systems and Thermal Storage*.
- IRENA, 2020. *Innovation outlook: Thermal energy storage*. Int. Renew. Energy Agency.
- ISO 14040, 2006. *Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Principles and framework*.
- Jensen, M.V., 2014. Seasonal pit heat storages - Guidelines for materials & construction, IEA-SHC TECH SHEET 45.B.3.2. <https://task45.iea-shc.org/data/sites/1/publications/IEA-SHC%20T45.B.3.2%20TECH%20Seasonal%20storages%20-%20Water%20Pit%20Guidelines.pdf>
- Jyvasjarvi, J., Marttila, H., Rossi, P.M., Ala-Aho, P.O.A., Olofsson, B., Nisell, J., Backman, B., Ilmonen, J., Virtanen, R., Paasivirta, L., Britschgi, R., Klove, B., Muotka, T., 2015. Climate-induced warming imposes a threat to north European spring ecosystems. *Glob. Change Biol.* 21, 4561–4569. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13067>

- Kabus, F., Richlak, U., Beuster, H., 2006. Saisonale Speicherung von Überschusswärme aus einem Heizkraftwerk in einem Aquifer in Neubrandenburg, in: Statusseminar „Thermische Energiespeicherung. Freiburg, Germany.
- Kapil, A., Bulatov, I., Smith, R., Kim, J.-K., 2012. Process integration of low grade heat in process industry with district heating networks. *Energy, Integration and Energy System Engineering, European Symposium on Computer-Aided Process Engineering 2011* 44, 11–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2011.12.015>
- Khasreen, M.M., Banfill, P.F.G., Menzies, G.F., 2009. Life-Cycle Assessment and the Environmental Impact of Buildings: A Review. *Sustainability* 1, 674–701. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su1030674>
- Klöpffer, W., Grahl, B., 2014. Life cycle assessment (LCA): a guide to best practice. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9783527655625>
- Kløve, B., Ala-Aho, P., Bertrand, G., Gurdak, J.J., Kupfersberger, H., Kværner, J., Muotka, T., Mykrä, H., Preda, E., Rossi, P., Uvo, C.B., Velasco, E., Pulido-Velazquez, M., 2014. Climate change impacts on groundwater and dependent ecosystems. *J. Hydrol., Climatic change impact on water: Overcoming data and science gaps* 518, 250–266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2013.06.037>
- Koellner, T., De, B.L., Beck, T., Brandao, M., Civit, B., Margni, M., Mila, I.C.L., Saad, R., Souza, D.M., Mueller-Wenk, R., 2013. UNEP-SETAC guideline on global land use impact assessment on biodiversity and ecosystem services in LCA. *Int. J. LIFE CYCLE Assess.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-013-0579-z>
- Kovács, V.B., Szalainé Kaczkó, O.I., Cséfalvay, E., 2025. Lca of a Heat Storage System Using Phase Change Materials for Waste Heat Valorization. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5088587>
- Kudryavtsev, S.A., Valtseva, T.Y., Gavrilov, I.I., Kotenko, Z.I., Sokolova, N., 2021. Geotechnical monitoring bearing capacity boring pile foundations of bridge during permafrost degradation. *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.* 1928, 012057. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1928/1/012057>
- Labaran, Y.H., Mathur, V.S., Muhammad, S.U., Musa, A.A., 2022. Carbon footprint management: A review of construction industry. *Clean. Eng. Technol.* 9, 100531. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clet.2022.100531>
- Lee, K.S., 2013. Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage, in: Lee, K.S. (Ed.), *Underground Thermal Energy Storage*. Springer, London, pp. 59–93. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4471-4273-7_4
- Lehmpful, K., 2015. Auswirkungen thermischer Veränderungen infolge der Nutzung oberflächennaher Geothermie auf die Beschaffenheit des Grundwassers und seiner Lebensgemeinschaften – Empfehlungen für eine umweltverträgliche Nutzung. Umweltbundesamt. <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/publikationen/auswirkungen-thermischer-veraenderungen-infolge-der>
- Lieskoski, S., Koskinen, O., Tuuf, J., Björklund-Sänkiäho, M., 2024. A review of the current status of energy storage in Finland and future development prospects. *J. Energy Storage* 93, 112327. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2024.112327>
- Lüchinger, R., Hendry, R., Walter, H., Worlitschek, J., Schuetz, P., 2025. Cost Analysis for Large Thermal Energy Storage Systems. *ASME J. Eng. Sustain. Build. Cities* 6. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4069122>
- Mangold, D., Miedaner, O., Tziggili, E.P., Schmidt, T., Unterberger, M., Zeh, B., 2011. Technisch-wirtschaftliche Analyse und Weiterentwicklung der solaren Langzeit-Wärmespeicherung (No. 0329607N), Forschungsbericht zum BMU-Vorhaben. SOLITES.
- MÅRTENSSON, F., 2020. Här samlas fjärrvärme under berget. *Tidn. Energi.*
- Martínez Blanco, J., Finkbeiner, M., Inaba, A., 2015. Guidance on Organizational Life Cycle Assessment.
- Mesquita, L., McClenahan, D., Thornton, J., Carriere, J., Wong, B., 2017. Drake Landing Solar Community: 10 Years of Operation, in: *Proceedings of SWC2017/SHC2017*. Presented at the ISES Solar World Conference 2017 and the IEA SHC Solar Heating and Cooling Conference for Buildings and Industry

- 2017, International Solar Energy Society, Abu Dhabi, pp. 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.18086/swc.2017.06.09>
- Milani, A., Dessi, F., Bonaiuto, M., 2024. A meta-analysis on the drivers and barriers to the social acceptance of renewable and sustainable energy technologies. *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 114, 103624. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2024.103624>
- Miljø- og Ligestillingsministeriet, 2021. Bekendtgørelse om miljøvurdering af planer og programmer og af konkrete projekter. <https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/lta/2021/1376>
- Monzó, P., Lazzarotto, A., Acuña, J., Tjernström, J., Nygren, M., 2016. Monitoring of a borehole thermal energy storage in Sweden.
- Müller, D., Bott, C., Hagström, M., Bayer, P., 2026. Cavern thermal energy storage: State of play and prospects. *Appl. Energy* 404, 127141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2025.127141>
- Neidhardt, H., Shao, W., 2023. Impact of climate change-induced warming on groundwater temperatures and quality. *Appl. Water Sci.* 13, 235. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13201-023-02039-5>
- Nishar, A., Bader, M.K.-F., O’Gorman, E.J., Deng, J., Breen, B., Leuzinger, S., 2017. Temperature Effects on Biomass and Regeneration of Vegetation in a Geothermal Area. *Front. Plant Sci.* 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2017.00249>
- Nordell, B., Andersson, O., Rydell, L., Liuzzo-Scorpo, A., 2015. Long-term Performance of the HT-BTES in Emmaboda, Sweden.
- Novo, A.V., Bayon, J.R., Castro-Fresno, D., Rodriguez-Hernandez, J., 2010. Review of seasonal heat storage in large basins: Water tanks and gravel–water pits. *Appl. Energy* 87, 390–397. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2009.06.033>
- Nussbicker, J., Heidemann, W., Mueller-Steinhagen, H., 2006. Monitoring results and operational experiences for a central solar district heating system with Borehole Thermal Energy Store in Neckarsulm (Germany), in: ECOSTOCK, 10th. International Conference on Thermal Energy Storage, Richard Stockton College of New Jersey.
- Ochs, F., Lichtenfels, A., Koch, H., Heidemann, W., Müller-Steinhagen, H., 2007. Heißwasser-Erdbecken-Wärmespeicher mit freitragender Abdeckung für solare Nahwärmesysteme, in: OTTI 17. Presented at the Symposium Thermische Solarenergie, Bad Staffelstein. https://www.igte.uni-stuttgart.de/veroeffentlichungen/publikationen/publikationen_07-06.pdf
- Ochs, F., Nußbicker-Lux, J., Marx, R., Koch, H., Heidemann, W., Müller-Steinhagen, H., 2008. Solar assisted district heating system with seasonal thermal energy storage in Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen. *Lisb. EuroSun*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/225001165_Solar_assisted_district_heating_system_with_seasonal_thermal_energy_storage_in_Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen
- Olayiwola, K., Perera, S., Kagioglou, M., Jin, X., Sharafi, P., 2025. A PESTEL Analysis of Problems Associated with the Adoption of Offsite Construction: A Systematic Literature Review. *Buildings* 15, 2146. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings15132146>
- Paksoy, H., Snijders, A., Stiles, L., 2009. State-of-the-Art Review of Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage Systems for Heating and Cooling Buildings, in: Proceedings 11th International Conference on Thermal Energy Storage for Energy Efficiency and Sustainability. Stockholm, Sweden.
- Paksoy, H.O., Gürbüz, Z., Turgut, B., Dikici, D., Evliya, H., 2004. Aquifer thermal storage (ATES) for air-conditioning of a supermarket in Turkey. *Renew. Energy* 29, 1991–1996. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2004.03.007>
- Park, D., Kim, H.-M., Ryu, D.-W., Choi, B.-H., Sunwoo, C., Han, K.-C., 2013. The effect of aspect ratio on the thermal stratification and heat loss in rock caverns for underground thermal energy storage. *Int. J. Rock Mech. Min. Sci.* 64, 201–209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrmmms.2013.09.004>

- PlanEnergi, 2015. Long term storage and solar district heating. https://energiforskning.dk/files/slutrappporter/sol_til_fjernvarme_brochure_oplag_2_til_web01_0.pdf
- Previati, A., Crosta, G.B., 2021. Characterization of the subsurface urban heat island and its sources in the Milan city area, Italy. *Hydrogeol. J.* 29, 2487–2500. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10040-021-02387-z>
- PROTOCOL on the implementation of the Alpine Convention of 1991 in the field of soil conservation Soil Conservation Protocol, 2005.
- Radloff, R., 2015. Entwicklung der großen Solarthermie in Dänemark. *Wärmewende-Info.* https://www.aktivregion-shs.de/fileadmin/Download/Alte_Daten/Entwicklungsstrategie_2014/Waermewende/Waermewende-Info_16_Entwicklung_der_Soalrthermie_in_DK_end__2_.pdf
- Rambøll, 2023. Erdbecken-Wärmespeicher in Deutschland. Proj. - Energ. <https://www.ramboll.com/de-de/projekte/energie/erdbecken-warmespeicher-in-deutschland>
- Rambøll, 2015. South-Jutland Stores the Sun's Heat in the World's Largest Pit Heat Storage. Euroheat Power. <https://www.euroheat.org/dhc/knowledge-hub/south-jutland-stores-the-sun-s-heat-in-the-world-s-largest-pit-heat-storage>
- Rehbinder, G., 1988. Hot water storage in rock caverns. Swedish State Power Board.
- Riedel, T., 2019. Temperature-associated changes in groundwater quality. *J. Hydrol.* 572, 206–212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2019.02.059>
- Rosen, M.A., Koohi-Fayegh, S., 2017. *Geothermal Energy: Sustainable Heating and Cooling Using the Ground.* John Wiley & Sons. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119181002>
- Sadeghi, H., Jalali, R., Singh, R.M., 2024a. A review of borehole thermal energy storage and its integration into district heating systems. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 192, 114236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.114236>
- Sadeghi, H., Jalali, R., Singh, R.M., 2024b. A review of borehole thermal energy storage and its integration into district heating systems. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 192, 114236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.114236>
- Sagebrand, U., Nordström, C., Widarsson, B., 2024. Uppföljning: Av Värmelager I Bergrum.
- Saito, T., Hamamoto, S., Ueki, T., Ohkubo, S., Moldrup, P., Kawamoto, K., Komatsu, T., 2016. Temperature change affected groundwater quality in a confined marine aquifer during long-term heating and cooling. *Water Res.* 94, 120–127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2016.01.043>
- Sanner, B., 2003. Thermische Untergrundspeicherung auf höherem Temperaturniveau : Begleitforschung mit Messprogramm Aquiferspeicher Reichstag. Schlussbericht zum FuE-Vorhaben 0329809 B. <http://nbn-resolving.de/urn:nbn:de:hebis:26-opus-17952>
- Schindlbacher, A., Rodler, A., Kuffner, M., Kitzler, B., Sessitsch, A., Zechmeister-Boltenstern, S., 2011. Experimental warming effects on the microbial community of a temperate mountain forest soil. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 43, 1417–1425. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2011.03.005>
- Schmidt, T., 2019. Marstal district heating monitoring data evaluation for the years 2015-2017 (No. EUDP 64014-0121). Solites, Stuttgart. https://www.solar-district-heating.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Marstal-evaluation-report-2015-2017_2019.05.28.pdf
- Schmidt, T., Mangold, D., Müller-Steinhagen, H., 2004. Central solar heating plants with seasonal storage in Germany. *Sol. Energy, Solar World Congress 2001* 76, 165–174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2003.07.025>
- Schmidt, T., Müller-Steinhagen, H., 2004. Die solar unterstützte Nahwärmeversorgung mit saisonalem Aquifer-Wärmespeicher in Rostock- Ergebnisse nach vier Betriebsjahren. 5. Symposium

- Erdgekoppelte Wärmepumpen. 8 Geothermische Fachtag. Landau Ger. https://www.igte.uni-stuttgart.de/veroeffentlichungen/publikationen/publikationen_04-01.pdf
- Schmidt, T., Pauschinger, T., Sørensen, P.A., Snijders, A., Djebbar, R., Boulter, R., Thornton, J., 2018. Design Aspects for Large-scale Pit and Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage for District Heating and Cooling. *Energy Procedia*, 16th International Symposium on District Heating and Cooling, DHC2018, 9–12 September 2018, Hamburg, Germany 149, 585–594. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2018.08.223>
- Schmidt, T., Sørensen, P.A., 2018. https://planenergi.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/Schmidt-and-Soerensen_Monitoring-Results-from-Large-Scale-Heat-storages-.pdf
- Scholliers, N., Ohagen, M., Bossennec, C., Sass, I., Zeller, V., Schebek, L., 2024. Identification of key factors for the sustainable integration of high-temperature aquifer thermal energy storage systems in district heating networks. *Smart Energy* 13, 100134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.segy.2024.100134>
- Segura, E., Belmonte, L., Morales, R., Somolinos, J., 2023. A Strategic Analysis of Photovoltaic Energy Projects: The Case Study of Spain. *Sustainability* 15, 12316. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151612316>
- Shah, A.N., Tanveer, M., Shahzad, B., Yang, G., Fahad, S., Ali, S., Bukhari, M.A., Tung, S.A., Hafeez, A., Souliyanonh, B., 2017. Soil compaction effects on soil health and cropproductivity: an overview. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 24, 10056–10067. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-017-8421-y>
- Shaver, G.R., Canadell, J., Chapin, F.S., Gurevitch, J., Harte, J., Henry, G., Ineson, P., Jonasson, S., Melillo, J., Pitelka, L., Rustad, L., 2000. Global Warming and Terrestrial Ecosystems: A Conceptual Framework for Analysis: Ecosystem responses to global warming will be complex and varied. Ecosystem warming experiments hold great potential for providing insights on ways terrestrial ecosystems will respond to upcoming decades of climate change. Documentation of initial conditions provides the context for understanding and predicting ecosystem responses. *BioScience* 50, 871–882. [https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568\(2000\)050%255B0871:GWATEA%255D2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568(2000)050%255B0871:GWATEA%255D2.0.CO;2)
- Sifnaios, I., 2023. Investigations of pit thermal energy storages in district heating systems. Technical University of Denmark, Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark.
- Sifnaios, I., Furbo, S., Jensen, A.R., 2025. Monitoring data of the Høje Taastrup water pit thermal energy storage. *Data Brief* 58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2025.111305>
- Sifnaios, I., Gauthier, G., Trier, D., Fan, J., Jensen, A.R., 2023a. Dronninglund water pit thermal energy storage dataset. *Sol. Energy* 251, 68–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2022.12.046>
- Sifnaios, I., Jensen, A.R., 2025. Performance analysis of the Høje Taastrup water pit thermal energy storage. *J. Energy Storage* 131, 117504. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2025.117504>
- Sifnaios, I., Jensen, A.R., Furbo, S., Fan, J., 2023b. Heat losses in water pit thermal energy storage systems in the presence of groundwater. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 235, 121382. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2023.121382>
- Sifnaios, I., Sneum, D.M., Jensen, A.R., Fan, J., Bramstoft, R., 2023c. The impact of large-scale thermal energy storage in the energy system. *Appl. Energy* 349, 121663. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.121663>
- Sipilä, K., Ritola, J., 1990. Converting and old rock cavern oil storage to a heat storage in Oulu, in: *Finnish Advanced Energy Systems R&D: Program Review*. Helsinki University of Technology, pp. 41–42. <https://cris.vtt.fi/en/publications/converting-and-old-rock-cavern-oil-storage-to-a-heat-storage-in-o/>
- Smith, P., Cotrufo, M.F., Rumpel, C., Paustian, K., Kuikman, P.J., Elliott, J.A., McDowell, R., Griffiths, R.I., Asakawa, S., Bustamante, M., House, J.I., Sobocká, J., Harper, R., Pan, G., West, P.C., Gerber, J.S., Clark, J.M., Adhya, T., Scholes, R.J., Scholes, M.C., 2015. Biogeochemical cycles and biodiversity as key drivers of ecosystem services provided by soils. *SOIL* 1, 665–685. <https://doi.org/10.5194/soil-1-665-2015>

- Snijders, A.L., 2005. Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage in the Netherlands: Status beginning of 2005.
- Solarwärme Bracht, 2025. Solarwärme Bracht eG (SWB). https://www.solarwaerme-bracht.de/technik/Sonnenspeicher_Süd, 2025. Sonnenspeicher Süd - Klimafreundliche nachhaltige Wärme für den Großraum Graz. https://www.ichtus.steiermark.at/cms/dokumente/12973665_179561198/992b4118/04_Schweighofer_W%C3%A4rmespeicher_Weitendorf.pdf
- Sørensen, P.A., Wetzels, H., Holm, L., Rasmussen, A., From, N., 2023. Design and Construction of the Pit Thermal Energy Storage in Høje Taastrup. https://planenergi.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/FLEX_TES-Implementationreport_final_23.12.23.pdf
- Stemmler, R., Blum, P., Schüppler, S., Fleuchaus, P., Limoges, M., Bayer, P., Menberg, K., 2021. Environmental impacts of aquifer thermal energy storage (ATES). *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 151, 111560. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111560>
- Stocker, T.F., Qin, D., Plattner, G.-K., Tignor, M., Allen, S.K., Boschung, J., Nauels, A., Xia, Y., Bex, V., Midgley, P.M., 2013. IPCC, 2013: climate change 2013: the physical science basis. Contribution of working group I to the fifth assessment report of the intergovernmental panel on climate change. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA.
- Streit, K., Hagedorn, F., Hiltbrunner, D., Portmann, M., Saurer, M., Buchmann, N., Wild, B., Richter, A., Wipf, S., Siegwolf, R.T.W., 2014. Soil warming alters microbial substrate use in alpine soils. *Glob. Change Biol.* 20, 1327–1338. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12396>
- Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works — Core rules for environmental product declarations of construction products and services, 2017.
- Sütterlin, B., Siegrist, M., 2017. Public acceptance of renewable energy technologies from an abstract versus concrete perspective and the positive imagery of solar power. *Energy Policy* 106, 356–366. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2017.03.061>
- Tomasetta, C., 2025. Life Cycle Assessment of Underground Thermal Energy Storage Systems: Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage versus Borehole Thermal Energy Storage. <https://unitesi.unive.it/handle/20.500.14247/16618>
- Tomasetta, C., 2013. Life Cycle Assessment of Underground Thermal Energy Storage Systems Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage versus Borehole Thermal Energy Storage - Corso di Laurea magistrale.
- Tomigashi, A., Fujinawa, K., 2011. Enhanced Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage For Cooling And Heating Of Shinshu University Building Using A Nested Well System. <https://www.witpress.com/elibRARY/wit-transactions-on-ecology-and-the-environment/150/22546>
- TREASURE project, 2024. TREASURE | Demonstrating Large Pit Thermal Energy Storages [WWW Document]. TREASURE. URL <https://www.treasure-project.eu> (accessed 3.24.26).
- Ustawę z dnia 3 października 2008 r. o udostępnianiu informacji o środowisku i jego ochronie, udziale społeczeństwa w ochronie środowiska oraz o ocenach oddziaływania na środowisko, 2008.
- Vallin, S., Hakala, P., Ahlqvist, K., Hagström, M., Luoto, T., 2025. Thermal Characterization of Crystalline Rocks for Cavern Thermal Energy Storage Application. Presented at the Sixth EAGE Global Energy Transition Conference & Exhibition (GET 2025), European Association of Geoscientists & Engineers, pp. 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.3997/2214-4609.202521067>
- Vang Jensen, M., Nielsen, J.E., 2020. Seasonal pit heat storages - Guidelines for materials & construction - IEA SHC FACT SHEET 55.C-D2. <https://task55.iea-shc.org/fact-sheets>
- VDI 4640 Blatt 1, 2010. VDI 4640 Blatt 1 - Thermische Nutzung des Untergrunds - Grundlagen, Genehmigungen, Umweltaspekte. <https://www.vdi.de/richtlinien/details/vdi-4640-blatt-1-thermische-nutzung-des-untergrunds-grundlagen-genehmigungen-umweltaspekte>

- VDI 4640 Blatt 3, 2001. VDI 4640 Blatt 3 - Thermische Nutzung des Untergrunds; Unterirdische thermische Energiespeicher. <https://www.vdi.de/richtlinien/details/vdi-4640-blatt-3-thermische-nutzung-des-untergrunds-unterirdische-thermische-energiespeicher>
- Weise, J., Bott, C., Menberg, K., Bayer, P., 2026. Comprehensive life cycle assessment of selected seasonal thermal energy storage systems. *Renew. Energy* 256, 124232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2025.124232>
- Wernet, G., Bauer, C., Steubing, B., Reinhard, J., Moreno-Ruiz, E., Weidema, B., 2016. The ecoinvent database version 3 (part I): overview and methodology. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 21, 1218–1230. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-016-1087-8>
- Wheater, H., Evans, E., 2009. Land use, water management and future flood risk. *Land Use Policy, Land Use Futures* 26, S251–S264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2009.08.019>
- Wigstrand, I., 2009. The ATEs project – a sustainable solution for Stockholm-Arlanda airport, in: *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Thermal Energy Storage for Energy Efficiency and Sustainability*. Stockholm, Sweden.
- Winterscheid, C., Schmidt, T., 2019. Dronninglund district heating monitoring data evaluation for the years 2015-2017 (No. EUDP 64014-0121). Solites. https://www.solar-district-heating.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Dronninglund-evaluation-report-2015-2017_20190531.pdf
- Worm, J., 2017. <https://www.coolheating.eu/images/downloads/5-The-Integration-of-Large-Scale-Solar-Thermal-and-Heat-Pumps-in-District-Heating-Systems.pdf>
- Xiang, Y., Xie, Z., Furbo, S., Wang, D., Gao, M., Fan, J., 2022. A comprehensive review on pit thermal energy storage: Technical elements, numerical approaches and recent applications. *J. Energy Storage* 55, 105716. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2022.105716>
- Yang, T., Liu, W., Kramer, G.J., Sun, Q., 2021. Seasonal thermal energy storage: A techno-economic literature review. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 139, 110732. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.110732>
- Zhang, S., Bai, J., Zhang, G., Xia, Z., Wu, M., Lu, H., 2023. Negative effects of soil warming, and adaptive cultivation strategies of maize: A review. *Sci. Total Environ.* 862, 160738. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.160738>
- Zhao, C., Yan, J., Tian, X., Xue, X., Zhao, Y., 2023. Progress in thermal energy storage technologies for achieving carbon neutrality. *Carbon Neutrality* 2, 10. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43979-023-00050-y>
- Zinko, H., Hahn, T., 1994. The high temperature (95 deg C) water pit storage of Malung. <https://www.osti.gov/etdeweb/biblio/53517>
- ЗАКОН о процени утицаја на животну средину, 2024.

8. Appendix

8.1 Questionnaire

8.1.1 Introduction

Survey on Pit Thermal Energy Storage in District Heating Systems

This survey explores the environmental parameters that influence a PTES project.

Your input is highly appreciated and will contribute to advancing energy storage solutions for a more sustainable future.

 The survey takes **only 5 minutes** and your answers will be treated anonymously.

This survey has been developed within the framework of the TREASURE project. About the project: The TREASURE project is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101136095. The project aims to bridge the gap between research and practice in the field of thermal energy storage. More information: www.treasure-project.eu

8.1.2 Data Protection

Data Protection and Consent Statement

We take the protection of your personal data very seriously. All personal data will be processed in accordance with applicable data protection regulations, used solely for scientific purposes, and treated with strict confidentiality. The analysis of this survey will be carried out by the Energieinstitut an der Johannes Kepler University Linz.

I confirm that I have read and understood all the information in the **data protection and consent statement**. I agree to participate in the study and consent to the analysis of my data.

8.1.3 E-mail address

Please enter your email address

Your email is only used to avoid duplicate responses.

[E-Mail address]

8.1.4 Expertise with PTES

What experience do you have with PTES projects?	
<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Have been involved in the construction of a PTES project</i>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Participated in a feasibility study for a PTES project
<input type="checkbox"/>	Have been working on PTES topics for some time, but have not yet been directly involved in a project implementation
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research
<input type="checkbox"/>	No prior experience with PTES projects

8.1.5 Explanation

<p>Context As part of Deliverable 6.1, we conducted a literature review to identify environmental parameters that may be relevant to the construction and operation of a PTES system.</p> <p>Task Please rate the potential influence of PTES on each environmental parameter on a scale from 1 (very low) to 5 (very high).</p> <p>Structure The environmental parameters have been grouped by topic for clarity. At the end of the survey, you will also have the opportunity to suggest additional relevant parameters that may not be listed.</p>
--

8.1.6 First Level Question

<p>Category: Soil <i>(sealing, contamination, quality)</i></p>
<p>How significantly could a PTES project negatively impact soil resources? <i>Impact (1 low – 5 high)</i></p>

<p>Category: Water <i>(ground & surface water, pollution, water use)</i></p>
<p>How strong could the negative ecological effects of a PTES project be on water resources? <i>Impact (1 low – 5 high)</i></p>

<p>Category: Air & Climate <i>(construction & operational emissions, land change, microclimate)</i></p>
<p>How severe could the negative impacts of a PTES project be on air quality and climate? <i>Impact (1 low – 5 high)</i></p>

<p>Category: Flora & Fauna <i>(habitat loss, degradation & fragmentation, impact on ecologically sensitive and protected areas)</i></p>
<p>How substantial could the harmful ecological effects of a PTES project be on flora and fauna? <i>Impact (1 low – 5 high)</i></p>

<p>Category: Landscape <i>(land use, visual change)</i></p>
<p>How strongly could the landscape be negatively affected by a PTES project? <i>Impact (1 low – 5 high)</i></p>

<p>Category: Resource use <i>(material use, carbon footprint, recyclability)</i></p>
<p>How considerable are the environmental burdens caused by construction-related resource use within a PTES project? <i>Impact (1 low – 5 high)</i></p>

<p>Category: Waste & Deconstruction <i>(dismantling, recycling, handling of potentially contaminated materials/disposal)</i></p>
<p>How significant are the negative impacts of a PTES project arising from waste generation and deconstruction processes? <i>Impact (1 low – 5 high)</i></p>

<p>Category: Noise emissions <i>(construction & operation phase)</i></p>
<p>How severe could the harmful ecological impact of noise emissions from a PTES project be? <i>Impact (1 low – 5 high)</i></p>

<p>Category: Socio-ecological aspects <i>(Land-use conflicts where land could serve agricultural or recreational purposes)</i></p>
<p>How strongly could socio-ecological aspects be negatively affected by a PTES project? <i>Impact (1 low – 5 high)</i></p>

<p>Category: Light pollution <i>(impacts on humans & wildlife, construction & operation phase)</i></p>
<p>How considerable could the ecological harm from light pollution generated by a PTES project be? <i>Impact (1 low – 5 high)</i></p>

Open Question:

From your expert perspective, are there any environmental parameters that have not been included?

[Text]

8.1.7 Second Level Question

If any category in the first-level questions was rated 3 or higher, additional detailed questions related to that category were presented, as listed here.

Category: Soil

Since you previously rated soil as a highly influential ecological factor, please describe how a PTES project could negatively affect the sub-categories listed below.

Impact (1 low – 5 high)

Sealing & compaction	1	2	3	4	5
Excavation & contamination	1	2	3	4	5
Quality (warming, pH, moisture, (bio)chemistry)	1	2	3	4	5

Category: Water

You indicated that water is strongly affected as an ecological parameter. How would you evaluate the potential negative impacts of a PTES project on the sub-categories listed below?

Impact (1 low – 5 high)

Groundwater flow	1	2	3	4	5
Groundwater warming	1	2	3	4	5
Groundwater connectivity (connecting separated groundwater sources)	1	2	3	4	5
Groundwater pollution	1	2	3	4	5
Infiltration & stormwater runoff	1	2	3	4	5
Surface waters	1	2	3	4	5
Water use (competition with drinking water)	1	2	3	4	5

Category: Air & Climate

You rated air and climate as highly sensitive ecological parameters. Please specify how a PTES project could negatively impact each of the sub-categories listed below.

Impact (1 low – 5 high)

Construction & operational emissions	1	2	3	4	5
Land change	1	2	3	4	5
Microclimate	1	2	3	4	5

Category: Flora & Fauna

You rated flora and fauna as ecological parameters with significant sensitivity. Please assess the potential negative impacts of a PTES project on each of the sub-categories listed below.

Impact (1 low – 5 high)

Habitat loss	1	2	3	4	5
Habitat degradation	1	2	3	4	5
Habitat fragmentation	1	2	3	4	5
Ecologically sensitive and protected areas	1	2	3	4	5

Category: Landscape

You previously considered landscape a highly sensitive ecological parameter. Please indicate how a PTES project could negatively affect the sub-categories listed below.

Impact (1 low – 5 high)

Land use	1	2	3	4	5
Visual change	1	2	3	4	5

Category: Resource use

You indicated that resource use is a highly influential ecological parameter. Please evaluate the negative environmental burden a PTES project could create in each of the sub-categories listed below.

Impact (1 low – 5 high)

Material use	1	2	3	4	5
Environmental burdens of materials used	1	2	3	4	5
Recyclability of materials	1	2	3	4	5

Category: Waste & Deconstruction

You rated waste and deconstruction as ecological parameters with strong relevance. Please specify how a PTES project could negatively impact the sub-categories listed below.

Impact (1 low – 5 high)

Dismantling	1	2	3	4	5
Recycling	1	2	3	4	5
Potentially contaminated materials & disposal	1	2	3	4	5

Category: Noise emissions

You assessed noise emissions as a highly influential ecological parameter. Please assess the potential negative ecological effects of a PTES project on the sub-categories listed below.

Impact (1 low – 5 high)

Construction phase	1	2	3	4	5
Operation phase	1	2	3	4	5

Category: Socio-ecological aspects
 You previously rated socio-ecological aspects as highly influential. Please indicate how a PTES project could negatively affect the sub-categories listed below.
Impact (1 low – 5 high)

Land-use conflicts (agriculture)	1	2	3	4	5
Land-use conflicts (recreational areas)	1	2	3	4	5

Category: Light pollution
 You indicated that light pollution is a highly influential ecological parameter. Please specify how a PTES project could negatively impact the sub-categories listed below.
Impact (1 low – 5 high)

Impacts on humans	1	2	3	4	5
Impacts on wildlife	1	2	3	4	5

Open Question:
Are there any ecological parameters that were not covered in the survey? Do you have any other comments or feedback for us?

[Text]

8.1.8 End Page

Please click "Submit" to finish the survey!

We really appreciate your valuable input. Thank you!

This survey was conducted by the Energieinstitut an der Johannes Kepler Universität Linz.

